

Decision-Making Confidence, Cultural Intelligence, and Life Satisfaction of School Heads

Leobert Don C. Laforteza
Emilio Aguinaldo College–Cavite
donlaforteza10@gmail.com

Date Submitted:
January 10, 2026

Date Accepted:
February 5, 2026

Date Published:
February 17, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.18683622

ABSTRACT

The study examined the socio-demographic profile of private school heads and its significant influence on their decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence (CQ), while also testing the relationship between cultural intelligence and decision-making confidence. Using Multiple Regression, the study determined how socio-demographic characteristics influenced decision-making confidence and CQ, and how these factors, in turn, affected life satisfaction. Pearson Correlation was applied to assess the relationship between decision-making confidence and CQ. Results indicated that most school heads were female, aged 41–50, holding

Master's degrees with 14–20 years of service. They demonstrated very high confidence across all aspects of decision-making, exhibited very high cultural intelligence, and reported highly satisfactory personal and professional life. Socio-demographic characteristics were found to significantly influence decision-making confidence in academic leadership, guidance, human resource management, and external relations, as well as cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive and behavioral CQ. Additionally, a significant relationship was observed between external relations in decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence, particularly in motivational and behavioral CQ. Further, decision-making confidence in academic leadership, guidance, human resource management, and external relations, together with metacognitive and behavioral CQ, significantly influenced the personal and professional life satisfaction of the school heads. These findings suggest that both demographic factors and cultural intelligence contribute substantially to leadership effectiveness and life satisfaction, highlighting the importance of targeted professional development and cultural competence training for school administrators.

Keywords: *Socio-Demographic Profile, School Heads, Decision-Making Confidence, Cultural Intelligence, Life Satisfaction, Academic Leadership, Human Resource Management, Guidance, External Relations, Professional Development*

INTRODUCTION

As the educational trend moves fast, globalizes, and the workforce becomes more diverse, it is increasingly necessary to understand why there are some academic leaders who are good at decision-making and are more satisfied with their lives. In today's increasingly global and diverse work settings, the ability to function effectively in varied situations is important for teachers and school heads of educational institutions. Ang (2012) discussed that the success or failure of any institution may be rooted to the ability to adapt to different cultures and good decision-making skills most especially that the stakeholders are diverse. This condition is very evident specifically to school heads who are exposed to student, teachers, parents and stakeholders' diversity.

Private schools are becoming more diverse. Students who attend schools with a diverse population can develop an understanding of the perspectives of children from different backgrounds and learn to function in a multicultural, multiethnic environment. Yet, as schools become more diverse, demands increase to find the most effective ways to help all students succeed academically as well as learn to get along with each other. School heads are faced with the challenge of making decision which is culturally responsive for all students while not favoring one group over another. School heads therefore must strive to create an environment where all children feel valued and all children can learn.

Kidapawan City and Cotabato divisions are basically workplaces with diverse groups of various culture, tribes, religion, race and ethnicity. This increase in diversity may have consequences for the well-being of students, teachers and school heads and may generate social problems and decrease social cohesion (Putnam, 2007). However, UNESCO, (2001) states the importance of cultural diversity is not only for economic growth, but also as a means to achieve a more satisfactory intellectual, emotional, moral and spiritual existence.

While the world is becoming global, interconnected and economically interdependent, Cultural Intelligence is one the 21st Century key leadership traits. Cultural Intelligence of others provides insights about how best to interact with others in multi-cultural situations, engage in cross-cultural interactions appropriately, and perform effectively in culturally diverse work groups. Therefore, lack of awareness on Cultural Intelligence on the part of the school head might lead to ineffectiveness in leading.

School heads have always needed intelligence. IQ helps them to handle facts and analyze problems, but it may not help them to manage people. So, then came Emotional Intelligence. EQ helps school heads to understand people, but often, only people who are like them. In the modern world, successful leaders also need to work with people who are not like them; people from different backgrounds, sectors, geographies, and generations.

Thus, studying the socio-economic status and exploring the cultural intelligence of a school head can be a springboard for a broader understanding about how this might relate and influence to their decision-making confidence and life satisfaction. Therefore, this study about the decision-making confidence, cultural intelligence, and life satisfaction of the school heads is a timely study. Moreover, the conduct of this study is essential to be able to identify whether the socio-demographic profile have influence to the

decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence of the respondents. Furthermore, it also identifies the relationship of the cultural intelligence to the decision-making confidence; and the influence of the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction of the school heads.

Statement of the Problem

The study determined the influence of the socio-demographic profile to the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence of the respondents. Furthermore, it mainly determined the relationship of the cultural intelligence to the decision-making confidence; influence of the decision-making confidence and the cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction of the school heads.

The study answered the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: age, gender, ethnicity, years in service, and highest educational attainment?
2. What is the decision-making confidence level of the respondents in terms of: academic leadership, governance, guidance and human resource management, financial and infrastructure management and external relations?
3. What is the cultural intelligence of the respondents in terms of: metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral intelligence?
4. What is the life satisfaction level of the respondents in terms of personal and professional aspects?
5. Does the socio-demographic profile of the respondents have a significant influence to their decision-making confidence?
6. Does the socio-demographic profile of the respondents have a significant influence to their cultural intelligence?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the cultural intelligence and the decision-making confidence of the respondents?
8. Does the decision-making confidence influence the life satisfaction of the respondents?
9. Does the cultural intelligence influence the life satisfaction of the respondents?

Significance of the Study

The study determined the socio-demographic profile have influence to the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence of the respondents. Furthermore, it also identified the relationship of the cultural intelligence to the decision-making confidence; the influence of the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction of the school heads.

In addition, this study will provide significant information to the following:

The Administrators. This study can inspire every administrator to strengthen educational researchers in the school. Moreover, the findings of this study may help administrators to be aware of the cultural characteristics of their subordinates, their decision-making confidence and level of life satisfaction.

The Academic Leaders. It is the researcher's hope that this study can somehow contribute to academic leaders in upgrading their level of cultural intelligence to effectively adapt to the diverse culture of their followers, effectively make decisions and be more aware of what makes their lives satisfied.

The Researcher. The findings of the study will serve as an assessment for academic leaders. It will provide inspiration to continue on conducting researches to help academic leaders cope up with the fast-changing educational system, globalization and diverse workforce.

The Society. Through this study the society, specifically the Region XII will be aware of the academic leaders' cultural intelligence, decision-making confidence and life satisfaction, thus, they will be aware of who are leading their children's education, understand where they are coming from so it will extend its hand in understanding and supporting the academic leaders.

The Country. The findings of the study may help the national government realized what needs to be focused on for our academic leaders to be able to adapt to diverse workforce, to have a high level of confidence in decision-making and have a more satisfied life to have a more successful leadership because they are the front liners in giving quality education in the children, thus, the resources for the country to be economically and politically competitive.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The research study involved a total of 30 private school principals or school heads from two divisions; Fifteen (15) from Cotabato Division and fifteen (15) from Kidapawan City Division within the school year 2016-2017. The School heads answered the Socio-demographic profile and Life Satisfaction questionnaires. The questionnaires for Decision-making and Cultural Intelligence were answered by the teachers. Complete enumeration of teachers was used in this study.

Moreover, the researcher had a one-on-one interview to some selected school heads in order to gather additional data and further validate the result of the study.

Operational Definition of Terms

For clarity and understanding, the following important terms are defined operationally:

Cultural Intelligence. It refers to a person's capability to function effectively in situations characterized by cultural diversity.

Cultural Intelligence-Behavior This phrase refers to a person's capability to adapt verbal and nonverbal behavior so it is appropriate for different cultures.

Cultural Intelligence-Cognitive. This phrase refers to a person's general knowledge and understanding about economic and legal systems, norms, religious beliefs, values, and language of different cultures.

Cultural Intelligence-Metacognitive. This phrase refers to how a person makes sense of inter-cultural experiences which reflects the individuals higher order thinking.

Cultural Intelligence-Motivation. This phrase refers to a person's interest in experiencing other cultures and interacting with people from different cultures.

Decision-making. This phrase refers to the thought process of selecting a logical choice from the available options.

Department of Education. This is the executive department of the Philippine government responsible for ensuring access to, promoting equity in, and improving the quality of basic education.

External Relations. This refers to a relation between a school to any entities such that if they had not been in this relation to each other.

Governance. This refers to processes of leading of the school head over a school system.

Life Satisfaction. This phrase refers to an overall assessment about the personal and professional life contentment of the school heads.

School Head. This refers to the person responsible for the administrative and instructional supervision of a private school or cluster of private schools who may be principals, administrator, director, head teachers, or teacher-in-charge by designation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age

In the study of Hora, (2014) entitled "Factors that affect Women Participation in Leadership and Decision-making Position", it was observed that majority of the respondents were accounted to be male. This implies that, the involvement of women in institutions is seen low. Majority of total respondents indicated as women are underrepresented in public leadership and decision-making positions. The finding showed that the major factors that hinder women's participation in public leadership and decision-making positions are various and observed interrelated. These include: lack (absence of adequate) educational status

required from women, absence of commitment by the concerned (top decision-making) body, backward sociocultural attitudes, lack of sufficient experiences from women to hold the leading positions, overburden of domestic responsibilities, as well as negative attitudes of men towards women, and lack of confidence from women themselves.

Jiang, et al., (2016) said that, although, the older generations were the very first to come into leadership, the younger generations can create a more sustainable development towards management, thus, younger generations will face a different set of challenges versus the older generations and that according to Worthy (2011) although older adults, who have a vast reserve of decision-making experience to draw upon, they often perform worse, and rarely perform better than younger adults in decision-making tasks.

An alternative reason maybe because the ability to make rational choices changes with age that older adults were not making too cautious choices, as is traditionally assumed (Scutti, 2013). In fact, the choices of elders might be seen as much too risky. An alternative possibility is that the tasks often used to assess age-based effects on decision-making are biased toward the strengths of younger adults and older adults' abilities may be better suited for situations that require higher-order processing of relational dependencies between the sequence of recent choices and the rewards currently available in the environment (Worthy, 2011).

Taylor (2016) study entitled, "Age and Experience as Determinants of Decision-making Performance", reveals that differences in managerial decision-making performance due to age and decision-making experience were investigated. Age was found to influence performance more than did prior decision-making experience. Little evidence was found to support the notion that older managers are less facile information processors and decision makers.

Gender

Women make up half of the human resources available to any country. If that half is not being channeled into the economy and not being made part of decision-making processes, then that country's economic potential is bound to suffer, by losing 50% of its capacity. As business leaders and policy-makers seek to navigate their way through the current economic crisis, they need the aggregate talents of both women and men more than ever to come up with the best solutions." A nation's competitiveness depends significantly on whether and how it educates and utilizes its female talent. To maximize its competitiveness and development potential, each country should strive for gender equality (Shamir & Eliam, 2005).

Men can be characterized as more confident than women especially regarding financial decisions. Men traded in greater volumes than do women, and as a result, make greater losses. Women's lower confidence, especially regarding financial matters, is also reflected in the fact that businesswomen generally report lower levels of profitability (Patel, 2013).

Interestingly, the gender differences do not seem to be completely linked to biological and neurological determinants. It does seem to be related to patriarchal societies. The Khasi tribe, a strong matriarchic society showed the opposite finding, thus that women were greater risk takers and more

competitive. It is observed that women are not only disadvantaged with respect to participating in decision-making but also in attaining higher educational levels. It is revealed that, as one goes up in public organizational leadership decision-making positions, the concentration of women decreases, whereas the opposite becomes real in lower organizational levels; hence, women are underrepresented (Gneezy, et al. 2009).

The participation of women in decision-making positions of community-based organizations is observed low, the encouragements made by political parties in the town administration for the participation of women in public leadership and decision-making position is judged good. Participating women in public leadership and decision-making is not only an important issue for the development of the nation, it is mandatory and pre-requisite for the prevalence of good governance as well as keeping basic human and political rights. As the study indicated, women affair office is being challenged to execute its mandates due to lack of adequate skilled manpower, lack of adequate budget allocation by the town administration, lack of clear enforcement mechanisms to implement affirmative actions uniformly across the public institutions, insufficient support by the concerned bodies, attitudinal problems on the parts of male colleagues and officials, lack of gender mainstreaming in various offices and the like.

In a study conducted (Hora, 2014), it is concluded that women are not only kept away from higher leadership positions, but also from access to higher education which makes them develop skills, and capacitate them with managerial decision-making techniques, help them develop confidence in holding leadership positions. The finding of the study indicated that the majority of respondents confirmed that if favorable conditions are set at place and women are provided the position to lead, they are as effective and successful as or more than that of their male

Yap, (2011) found that women spent three times longer on domestic chores, such as cooking, cleaning and washing, than their husbands or partners. Some female breadwinners, however, have to shoulder the burden of all the housework as almost one in five men admitted to doing nothing at all around the home. The average for women was 17 hours a week, compared to just less than six hours for men. But more than a quarter of wives and girlfriends spend more than 21 hours a week on domestic chores. These times exclude childcare, which is also traditionally far more likely to fall on women. The findings come despite the best intentions of most men, who agreed that they should share the burden by doing more housework.

Apparently, Croson and Gneezy, (2009) noted that men today do a higher share of chores and household work than any generation of men before them. Yet working women, especially working mothers, continue to do significantly more. Catalyst (2007) compared Fortune 500 companies on the representation of women on their boards and their corporate performance. They found that when comparing the worst and best quartile of female representation this had significant effects on the institution. Return on Equity increased by 53%, Profit Margin by 42%, and Return on Invested Capital by 66%. They also found that a minimum of three women on the board gave the best results.

McKinsey (2007) confirms this relationship. They find that companies with the highest gender diversity teams, as compared to the industry average, see a much higher Return on Equity, a higher operating

result, and a stronger stock price growth. In addition, having at least one woman on the board decreases bankruptcy. Interestingly, companies with more women on their boards see better corporate governance and ethical behavior.

There is hardly a difference between senior men and women when aspiring for the highest roles in the company (Catalyst, 2004). Furthermore, women struggle with so-called second-generation gender biases, which are “powerful yet often invisible barriers to women’s advancement that arise from cultural beliefs about gender, as well as workplace structures, practices, and patterns of interactions that 10 inadvertently favor men”. These second-generation gender biases have recently been discussed as causes for women’s underrepresentation on boards.

According to Acharya et al., (2010) women's autonomy in decision-making is positively associated with their age, employment and number of living children. Women from rural area and Terai region have less autonomy in decision-making in all four types of outcome measure. There is a mixed variation in women's autonomy in the development region across all outcome measures. Western women are more likely to make decision in own health care, while they are less likely to purchase daily household needs. Women's increased education is positively associated with autonomy in own health care decision-making, however their more schooling shows non-significance with other outcome measures. Interestingly, rich women are less likely to have autonomy to make decision in own. Women from rural area and Terai region needs specific empowerment programme to enable them to be more autonomous in the household decision-making. Women's autonomy by education, wealth quintile and development region need a further social science investigation to observe the variations within each stratum. In a study conducted by Groyberg, 2013, he said that women are shown to have positive effects that improve corporate performance.

Ethnicity

Ethnicity is a part of an individual’s cultural identity and have profound effects on organizations. The source of cultural differences is less important than the different values and perspectives that emerge from these differences. Understanding cultural protocols is helpful, but what matters more is understanding the cultural differences in how people communicate, plan and execute tasks. How today’s leaders integrate the expectations and work styles of four generations, a dozen nationalities and many subcultures to achieve a shared vision and shared strategies for an organization (Gneezy, et al. 2009).

National culture most strongly shapes most people’s thinking and behavior. In many organizations, people sit in lunchrooms separated by functions: IT people eat with other IT people, engineers eat with other engineers. The same scenario is observed in within companies, the lunchrooms are more likely to be segregated according to nationality, with Indians seated together at one table, Chinese at another and Australians at yet another. Ethnicity is only one of several cultural spheres that influence what happens inside organizations (McKinsey, 2007).

Years in Service

In education, teacher experience is probably the key factor in personnel policies that affect current employees: it is a cornerstone of traditional single-salary schedules; it drives teacher transfer policies that prioritize seniority; and it is commonly considered a major source of inequity across schools and, therefore, a target for redistribution (Harris and Sass, 2007). Experience matters, but more is not always better. The impact of experience is strongest during the first few years of teaching; after that, marginal returns diminish. A number of studies confirm findings from existing research that, on average, brand new teachers are less effective than those with some experience under their belts (Ladd, 2008),

Early-career experience has a clear payoff in teacher effectiveness, in which the impact is stronger than the effect of most other observable teacher-related variables including advanced degrees, teacher licensure tests scores, National Board certification at the elementary level, and class size (Clotfelter et al. 2007). Teachers show the greatest productivity gains during their first few years on the job, after which their performance tends to level off. A study using New York City data illustrates the diminishing marginal returns to experience (Ladd, 2008).

Further, the differential attrition of teachers with different levels of effectiveness may confound findings about the effects of teacher experience. While some evidence suggests that teachers who remain teaching after three years are less effective on average than those who leave, other research has found that less effective teachers are more likely to transfer and leave teaching, (Harris and Sass, 2007). These conflicting findings raise questions about whether the measured effects of experience reflect improvement with experience or higher attrition of less effective teachers (Sass et al. 2010).

On average, teachers with more than 20 years of experience are more effective than teachers with no experience, but are not much more effective than those with 5 years of experience, (Ladd, 2008). Studies have also documented some evidence that effectiveness declines after some point, particularly among high school teachers. Evidence suggests that the most experienced (greater than 25 years) teachers may be less effective than their less experienced counterparts (Ladd 2008) and even their inexperienced colleagues. According to one study using data from North Carolina, elementary school teachers with one or two years of experience are more effective, on average, than teachers with no experience (Harris and Sass, 2007).

Given the general finding that teacher experience or more accurately, teacher inexperience is systematically related to teacher productivity. Studies offer compelling evidence of an uneven distribution of inexperienced teachers that is systematically related to school and student characteristics. Teachers with three or fewer years of experience (those shown to be less effective, on average) are more likely to be teaching in high-poverty schools (Clotfelter et al. 2007).

The decline in performance among the most experienced teachers is most evident, suggesting that this is where such attention should be focused. In cases where more veteran teachers are unable to maintain performance levels with adequate support and professional development, mechanisms for alternative assignments or even dismissal should be considered. The evidence that the most experienced teachers may not be the most effective should prompt policymakers to reexamine the common practice of determining

teacher layoffs based on seniority. This is not to say seniority is not important, but such policies may undermine efficiency (Sass et al. 2010).

Highest Educational Attainment

In some western countries over 50% of graduates are women. For instance, in the UK, more than 54% of the postgraduates were female. However, this is not the case for countries like India, Pakistan and South Africa, but surprisingly so in countries such as Saudi Arabia. (European Commission, 2012). In the Netherlands, good education is seen as a pre-requisite for a good life, but the highly educated appear slightly less satisfied with life in comparison to their less educated counterparts. The level of educational attainment for individuals is considered a key socioeconomic indicator. Higher educational attainment can lead to improved access to social resources including improved employment opportunities (ABS, 1998). Globally, although more boys are enrolled at primary and secondary education, more women are educated at tertiary level. However, for countries such as India, Pakistan, and Nigeria, women are enrolled at lower rates in tertiary education, (European Commission, 2012).

Access to education promotes independence, reduces boredom and frustration, maximizes individual potential and is a fundamental human right which must be upheld and safeguarded. Through participation in education, people with impaired decision-making capacity experience not only an important element of social inclusion, but also the opportunity to enter life transitions such as progression to post-school employment, or education, or other meaningful day activity (Office of the Public Advocate, 2012).

Decision-making Confidence

Decision-making is a crucial ingredient to education administration because a school, like all formal organizations, is basically a decision-making structure. Decision-making is a process that guides actions (Martin, Et al., (2012). Decisions are based on the beliefs, cultural intelligence, values and previous experiences of individuals. Leaders must know themselves, know why they choose particular paths, know whom to involve, and know which particular decision-making model to use (Earley, Ang, and Tan 2006).

The 5 key responsibilities of School heads according to The Wallace Foundation, (2013): Shaping a vision of academic success for all students, one based on high standards; Creating a climate hospitable to education in order that safety, a cooperative spirit and other foundations of fruitful interaction prevail; Cultivating leadership in others so that teachers and other adults assume their parts in realizing the school vision; Improving instruction to enable teachers to teach at their best and students to learn to their utmost; and Managing people, data and processes to foster school improvement.

Earley and Ang, (2003) said that distorted decision-making are clearly less valuable as an indicator of apparent quality of life. Nevertheless, inappropriate life-satisfaction is still life-satisfaction. The concept of life satisfaction is not limited to judgements which are considered to be correct by others, but in essence relies on the person's own decision-making. Uncertain and unstable decision-making are clearly less valuable as an indicator of quality of life. Still such judgements denote life-satisfaction. Furthermore, appraisals of life are probably not always equally appropriate. Like any perception they can be distorted in

various ways, such as through mis-attribution and self-deceit. This is commonly referred to as ‘false happiness’ (Kong, et al., 2012).

Academic leadership

Kanter and Zimmerman (2012) stated that leaders do not make decisions in isolation — nor are the implications of their decisions inconsequential. Leaders make decisions with others either for others, against others, or with others in mind with the goal of changing that social context, ideally for the “better,” but often with the risk that their decisions may have negative effects or collateral implications. Advanced Leaders make decisions from the top, from a position of authority, and at other times they must make choices from the bottom, with limited means for aligning goals, influencing stakeholders or marshaling resources, but with a larger social objective in mind. Decisions initiate actions.

It is inevitable that leaders, no matter what type, will be faced with many different decisions. Some decisions will be minor and may not affect anyone but themselves. Other decisions can be quite large and have the capacity to affect everyone and anyone under their leadership, (Taylor, 2016). Decision-making is part of a leader’s daily expectations. This makes decision-making important for those in a leadership role. Leaders have a responsibility to make good decisions for everyone involved, and therefore, should have some kind of framework for which to make those decisions. Decision-making can be difficult, especially for those in positions of leadership. Making the wrong decision can impact the bottom line of the business or organization, it can turn people against a leader, and it can cause many other people to be affected. Leaders should consider what decision framework they use, as well as the ethical standards and principles of the business, as well as their own when making a decision. However, leaders should not be afraid to make a decision, as it is a key component to being a leader (Deniz, 2004).

Ejimabo, (2015) reported that leadership decision-making among other qualities and functions of a leader offers an ongoing creativity and important new insights into leadership and management activities in all organizational operations. The results that emerged from the data indicated that there is a great need for change and improvement in decision-making among organizational executives while accommodating technology, diversity, globalization, policy, teamwork, and leadership effectiveness. . In this regard and for effectiveness, a leader must have self-confidence in order to gather and process information and solve problems. For them a person riddled with self-doubt would never be able to take the necessary actions nor command the respect of others. Leaders must know what decisions to make and keep the interest of all stakeholders involved.

Further, the inabilities of some leaders in developing good policy standards, knowledge, basis, protocols, environments, and skill that incorporate support and optimal decision design for their organizations is troubling and have caused the closure of many business in the country due to either law suit or mismanagement. Another significant problem that encouraged this work is the lack of knowledge on how to design positive decision environment, healthy communication skills, and essential tools for leadership decision-making in the entire organization. Many leadership practitioners and scholars believed that any organization faced with negative policy and decisions by its leadership and management will continue to fail, their people will be often left to ponder the cause, and that organization would be

unproductive in their business while giving way to employees to break the circle for both job performance and goal accomplishment (Ejimado, 2015).

Furthermore, creative policy development and decision-making among organizational leaders and management are of vital importance to the growth, development, and success of any business establishments. For instance, choosing the best alternative from many alternatives and making a good decision in critical matters and challenging situations is always a good strategy of solving problems in most organizations. Thus, the problem in most organizations is that problems tend to present themselves in non-associated symptoms (Deniz, 2006).

Governance

In this global, interconnected and economically interdependent world Cultural Intelligence is becoming one of the key leadership traits of the 21st century. Understanding national cultures and their impact on organizational flows and effective relationships building, is critical in establishing a truly integrated global culture. As reported, the companies localize management, they also need to be more globally integrated and do so effectively, making global perspective one of the most important qualities for modern leaders (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2010).

Cultural intelligence or CQ is measured on a scale, similar to that used to measure an individual's intelligence quotient. People with higher CQs are regarded as better able to successfully blend into any environment, using more effective business practices, than those with a lower CQ. Cultural intelligence is assessed using the academically validated assessment created by Linn Van Dyne and Soon Ang. Both self-assessments and multi-rater assessments are available through the Cultural Intelligence Center in East Lansing, Michigan and the Center makes the CQ Scale available to other academic researchers at no charge.

The four dimensions of CQ are qualitatively different facets of the overall capability to function and manage effectively in culturally diverse settings (Earley and Ang, 2003). Like facets of life satisfaction, the dimensions of CQ may or may not correlate with each other. Thus, overall CQ represents an aggregate multidimensional construct, which according to Law et al. (1998) includes: (i) dimensions at the same level of conceptualization as the overall construct; and (ii) dimensions make up the overall construct. In sum, metacognitive CQ, cognitive CQ, motivational CQ and behavioural CQ are different capabilities that together form overall CQ.

Guidance and Human Resource Management

Earley and Ang, (2003) said that in today's global economy, human resource professionals, managers and employees work with people from a variety of cultural backgrounds daily. Who should adapt to whom, and how can organizations make the most of the burgeoning diversity across the workforce?

Many employees encounter awkward and confusing situations on a regular basis. For example: You're talking to a person from a different culture, and he doesn't look you in the eye. Is it a cultural difference or a personal quirk? How do you know, and how do you deal with it? You're ready to sign a

contract after months of intense negotiations with a new international client. At the eleventh hour, the client puts everything on hold and says she needs to get back to you in two weeks (Raabe, et. al, 2007).

Financial and Infrastructure Management

Hansraj (2007), said that the responsibility for the accuracy of the financial records lies with the principal, even if he or she does not have the task of maintaining the financial records on a regular basis. The principal is required by regulations to make numerous and frequent monthly and weekly checks on the income and expenditure status of the school. The role of the principal with regard to school financial management is an important aspect of the overall management of the school. The roles of principals now include being accountable for the financial records of their school. The principal holds ultimate responsibility to ensure that the work is done. Then he or she may delegate one member to do a particular task (example look after the administration of the school fees). Of course, the principal must ensure that the delegated member/s have a clear understanding of what is expected of them. The principal keeps ultimate responsibility and accountability, so he or she must make sure that the work is done properly (Naidoo, 2006).

In terms of the changing role of the principal with reference to financial school management, on the positive side, the changed role for principals will allow principals to become much more aware of the financial cost of education (Hansraj, 2007). Principals have become more responsive to the demands of all those involved in education and they are able to have a tighter reign on the finances of the school and are able to say 'no' rather than shift the blame. On the other end of the stick, it is possible that principals have less contact and teaching time. From the study it has been found that many schools lack the finances to employ a bursar to take up the increased administrative tasks such as monitoring the collection of monies, banking etcetera.

Cranston (2002) found out in a study that principals must now add to their repertoire of skills, financial expertise, resource management, detailed understanding of building and maintenance issues, knowledge of accountancy, considerable committee expertise and a range of management skills that are traditionally not been expected of them.

External Relations

Little (2011a) asked schools to work in partnership with community- and faith-based organizations to support children's learning during the hours after school and during the summertime. Consequently, there has been tremendous growth across the nation in intentional efforts to forge meaningful partnerships between schools and afterschool and summer programs. Strong and sustainable partnerships need relationships that are built at multiple levels (for example, at the district, school, and classroom levels) and among multiple school staff, including district and nonteaching staff. Working with partners at different levels helps the afterschool and summer programs become integral to the daily life and culture of the school at all levels, from the principal to the custodian.

Cranston, (2009) postulated that external relationships at various levels have to help mitigate the effects of staff turnover at other levels; for example, strong relationships with teachers can help sustain the partnership in the event of a change in principals. One feature of a strong collaboration is the ability of partners to access information and data from each other, including, if possible, student-level academic data (e.g., test scores and grades).

When schools and community organizations work together to support learning, everyone benefits. Partnerships can serve to strengthen, support, and even transform individual partners, resulting in improved program quality, more efficient use of resources, and better alignment of goals and curricula. Partnerships can have additional benefits to students and their families. They can provide continuity of services across the day and year, easing school transitions and promoting improved attendance in after school programs; facilitate access to a range of learning opportunities and developmental supports, providing opportunities for students and teachers alike to experiment with new approaches to teaching and learning; facilitate information sharing about specific students to best support individual learning; and provide family members with alternative entry points into the school day to support their student's learning (Neild, et al. 2004).

Learning partnerships can also greatly benefit schools. They can complement the academic curriculum with a wider range of services and activities, particularly enrichment and arts activities that may not be available during the school day; support transitions across the school years, particularly the critical middle to high school transition, which research indicates is a key predictor of high school graduation (Neild, et al. 2007); reinforce concepts taught in school without replicating the school day, often exposing classroom teachers working in the after school program to new pedagogies; improve school culture and community image through exhibitions and performances that help "shine the light" on students whose talents may not be apparent in the classroom; and gain access to mentors, afterschool staff, and other resources to support in-school learning and improve the teaching and learning in the classroom itself.

Learning partnerships with schools can strengthen and support community partners. They can help gain access to and recruit groups of students most in need of support services; improve program quality and staff engagement, particularly when there is crossover between school and community organization staff; foster better alignment of programming to support a shared vision for learning, one which aligns curriculum to support state and local standards; and maximize resource use such as facilities, staff, data, and curriculum (Archaya, et al., 2010).

Most management teams in young technology companies are aware that their success may depend on strong relationships with external organizations. However, it may not be clear to them which types of relationships are most likely to impact their growth. Both researchers and management teams alike are increasingly recognizing the importance of a company's relationships, which include any interactions between a company and an external organization (Van & Janssens, 2011).

A relationship can be a customer or supplier relationship, or a relationship in which the firms work together directly, such as a joint venture or a marketing or business partnership. It can also include financial

relationships in which a firm receives financing in return for equity or other considerations. Increasingly, the field is recognizing that these partnerships are essential to efforts to expand when, where, how, and what students learn (Little, 2011b).

Cultural Intelligence

Cultural Intelligence (CQ) is a person's capability to function effectively in situations characterized by cultural diversity (Ang, Van Dyne, & Koh, 2005). Cultural Intelligence is the newest type of Intelligence that has recently hit the mainstreamed world. CQ differs from IQ and EQ because it is a critical capability that enhances an individual's success in cross-cultural settings. However, as opposed to an individual's static IQ, CQ is a capability that can grow and develop over time.

Van Dyne, Ang, and Livermore, (2010), underscored an individual's Cultural Intelligence depends on several factors and can be enhanced in many ways. It can change based on a person's interactions with other cultures, their effort and interest in learning about new cultures, as well as through international experiences. Awareness of other cultures can be gathered through educational, personal and work experiences. Cultural Intelligence is extremely beneficial as it provides insights into how individuals are able to handle interacting in cross-cultural situations. Enhancing one's CQ is critical for people who interact with multicultural co-workers, managers, trade partners, clients, etc. Also, it is important for increasing organizational effectiveness in multicultural teams at home.

Earley and Ang, (2003) anchored their discussion of the theoretical bases of CQ in contemporary theories of intelligence. Cultural intelligence (CQ), defined as an individual's capability to function and manage effectively in culturally diverse settings, is consistent with Schmidt and Hunter's (2000) definition of general intelligence as 'the ability to grasp and reason correctly with abstractions (concepts) and solve problems. Although early research tended to view intelligence narrowly as the ability to solve problems in academic settings, there is now increasing consensus that intelligence may be displayed in places other than the classroom. This growing interest in 'real world' intelligence includes intelligence that focuses on specific content domains such as social intelligence, emotional intelligence, and practical intelligence (Sternberg et. al., 2000).

CQ acknowledges the practical realities of globalization, Earley and Ang, (2003) focus on a specific domain – intercultural settings. Thus, following Schmidt and Hunter's (2000) definition of general intelligence, CQ is a specific form of intelligence focused on capabilities to grasp, reason and behave effectively in situations characterized by cultural diversity. Cultural intelligence can be understood as the capability to relate and work effectively across cultures. Originally, the term cultural intelligence and the abbreviation "CQ" was developed by the research done by Soon Ang and Linn Van Dyne, (2010) as a researched-based way of measuring and predicting intercultural performance.

Success in these situations requires a unique set of skills known as cultural competence. Organizations and managers sometimes dismiss cultural competence as a set of elusive, soft skills that cannot be measured or taught. But that is not the case. These skills can be developed, and a number of intercultural models and inventories exist that can help. This focused primarily on cultural intelligence

(CQ), an innovative, research-based approach for working effectively across national, ethnic and organizational cultures (Ang, 2010).

CQ-Drive is a person's interest and confidence in functioning effectively in culturally diverse settings. It includes: Intrinsic interest – deriving enjoyment from culturally diverse experiences; Extrinsic interest – gaining benefits from culturally diverse experiences; and Self-efficacy – having the confidence to be effective in culturally diverse situations. CQ-Knowledge is a person's knowledge about how cultures are similar and how cultures are different. It includes: Business – knowledge about economic and legal systems; Interpersonal – knowledge about values, social interaction norms, and religious beliefs; and Socio-linguistics – knowledge about rules of languages and rules for expressing non-verbal behaviors. CQ-Strategy is how a person makes sense of culturally diverse experiences. It occurs when people make judgments about their own thought processes and those of others. It includes: Awareness – knowing about one's existing cultural knowledge; Planning – strategizing before a culturally diverse encounter; Checking – checking assumptions and adjusting mental maps when actual experiences differ from expectations. CQ-Action is a person's capability to adapt verbal and nonverbal behavior to make it appropriate to diverse cultures. It involves having a flexible repertoire of behavioral responses that suit a variety of situations. It includes: Non-verbal – modifying non-verbal behaviors (e.g., gestures, facial expressions) and Verbal – modifying verbal behaviors (e.g., accent, tone) (Van Dyne, et al., 2010).

Additional research on cultural intelligence is being conducted by academics around the globe, including research on culturally intelligent organizations, the correlation between neuroscience and the development of cultural intelligence, and situational judgment making and CQ Assessment (Van Dyne, et al., 2007). Understanding customers across multiple contexts is one of the biggest challenges faced by senior executives. Cultural intelligence helps people understand the perspectives and priorities of others and work cooperatively to develop mutually acceptable decisions (Janssens, and Brett, 2006).

This is important because the common sense, lead-with-your-gut approach to making decisions that often works in a person's home culture does not work when leading culturally diverse groups or when functioning in a different culture. With high CQ—especially CQ Knowledge and CQ Strategy— people can diagnose situations from multiple perspectives and make effective decisions in culturally diverse contexts. Without the insights offered by cultural intelligence, employees are at a disadvantage when making strategic decisions, particularly in the midst of a crisis (Groves and Feyerherm, 2011).

Ziaaddini and Mahmudian (2013) stated in a research by Harvard University and humanism center of Indiana University, found that people having high cultural intelligence and better communication, are happier than people who are richer without desirable social relation. He also believed that cultural intelligence is really a strong anticipator to determine people happiness and life quality in society. So, to increase life satisfaction level, investing in cultural intelligence is more valuable. The ability of having good relation with others is one of the main resources of happiness. People who have high cultural intelligence can perceive others feelings well, make sympathy and communicate with them satisfactorily. They also don't make them angry by destroying others happy positions because they accept their independent feelings and respect.

Argel and Grosland (2011) believe that a satisfied person has a desirable perception and satisfies him/her self, balanced social relations and avoids hatred and hate and evaluates the life positively. Cultural intelligence is a new extends of intelligence which has high relation to workplace. Cultural intelligence allows people to learn how others think and how they respond to behavioral sample, so communicational obstacles are decreased and people receive cultural management.

Metacognitive CQ

Sternberg's (1986) integrative framework proposed different 'loci' of intelligence within the person. Metacognition, cognition and motivation are mental capabilities that reside within the head, while overt actions are behavioural capabilities. Metacognitive intelligence refers to control of cognition: the processes individuals use to acquire and understand knowledge.

Metacognitive CQ reflects mental processes that individuals use to acquire and understand cultural knowledge, including knowledge of and control over individual thought processes relating to culture. Relevant capabilities include planning, monitoring and revising mental models of cultural norms for countries or groups of people. Those with high metacognitive CQ are consciously aware of others' cultural preferences before and during interactions. They also question cultural assumptions and adjust their mental models during and after interactions (Brislin et al., 2006)

While metacognitive CQ focuses on higher-order cognitive processes, cognitive CQ reflects knowledge of the norms, practices and conventions in different cultures acquired from education and personal experiences. This includes knowledge of the economic, legal and social systems of different cultures and subcultures and knowledge of basic frameworks of cultural values. Those with high cognitive CQ understand similarities and differences across cultures (Chen et.al., 2000).

Cognitive CQ

Cognitive intelligence refers to knowledge structures and is consistent with intelligence-as-knowledge concept, which argues for the importance of knowledge as part of the intellect. Motivational intelligence refers to the mental capacity to direct and sustain energy on a particular task or situation and recognize that motivational capabilities are critical to 'real world' problem solving (Ang, et al. 2005).

In the study of Nielsen, et al. (2016) entitled, examined the mediating effect of career engagement on the relationship between cognitive cultural intelligence (CQ) and life satisfaction among international migrant workers in Australia. It also examines the moderating effect of perceived social injustice on the cognitive CQ–career engagement relationship, as well as on the indirect cognitive CQ–life satisfaction relationship via career engagement. Using survey data from four hundred and sixty-two migrant workers in Australia, it was found that cognitive CQ was positively related to life satisfaction and that career engagement mediated this relationship.

The indirect effect of cognitive CQ on life satisfaction via career engagement was also stronger for those perceiving higher social injustice. These findings provide new insights regarding the antecedents of

life satisfaction as well as reveal a vocationally relevant mechanism underlying the relationship between cognitive CQ and life satisfaction. The results inform potential practical strategies to enhance the career progression and life satisfaction of international migrant workers (Thomas, 2006).

Motivational CQ

Motivational CQ reflects the capability to direct attention and energy toward learning about and functioning in situations characterized by cultural differences. Motivational capacities ‘provide agentic control of effect, cognition and behavior that facilitate goal accomplishment.’ The direction and magnitude of energy channelled toward a particular task involves two elements – expectations of success and value of success. Those with high motivational CQ direct attention and energy toward cross-cultural situations based on intrinsic interest and confidence in their cross-cultural effectiveness (Dollwet and Reichard, 2014).

CQ-Motivation is a person’s interest in experiencing other cultures and interacting with people from different cultures. Motivational CQ is magnitude and direction of energy applied toward learning about and functioning in cross-cultural situations. It includes the intrinsic value people place on culturally diverse interactions as well as their sense of confidence that they can function effectively in settings characterized by cultural diversity (Ng, 2009).

People have always needed intelligence. IQ helps them to handle facts and analyze problems, but it may not help them to manage people. So then came Emotional Intelligence. EQ helps school leaders to understand people, but often, only people who are like them. In the modern world, successful leaders also need to work with people who are not like them; people from different backgrounds, sectors, geographies, and generations. Modern leaders need Cultural Intelligence, CQ. Cultural Intelligence (CQ) is the natural evolution from the well-established notions of IQ (intelligence quotient) and EQ (emotional intelligence). Good leaders need all three to lead effectively (Groves and Feyerherm, 2011).

According to Chen, et al., (2000) Cultural Intelligence is malleable and can be enhanced through experiences, education and training.

Behavioral CQ

Behavioral intelligence refers to outward manifestations or overt actions: what people do rather than what they think. Applying Sternberg’s multiple-loci of intelligence, Earley and Ang (2003) conceptualized CQ as comprising metacognitive, cognitive, motivational and behavioral dimensions with specific relevance to functioning in culturally diverse settings.

Behavioral CQ reflects the capability to exhibit appropriate verbal and nonverbal actions when interacting with people from different cultures. Mental capabilities for cultural understanding and motivation must be complemented with the ability to exhibit appropriate verbal and nonverbal actions, based on cultural values of specific settings. This includes having a wide and flexible repertoire of behaviors. Those with high behavioral CQ exhibit situationally appropriate behaviours based on their broad

range of verbal and nonverbal capabilities, such as exhibiting culturally appropriate words, tone, gestures and facial expressions (Earley and Ang, 2003).

Jaafari (2008) also believe that haven suitable social relations and proportionate to organization culture and ability to communicate with colleagues is the biggest resource of happiness. Having a happy life and enjoyable association needs basic skills and learning them. So, creating a friendly relation and feeding happiness need social and mental skills.

CQ-Behavior is a person's capability to adapt verbal and nonverbal behavior so it is appropriate for different cultures. It includes having a flexible repertoire of behavioral responses that are appropriate in a variety of situations and having the capability to modify both verbal and nonverbal behavior based on those involved in a specific interaction or in a particular setting (Earley and Ang, 2003).

Cultural intelligence which determines the manners of person behaviors in workplaces Influences feeling of satisfaction and sorrow in people. Considering someone cultural intelligence and that how he/she controls and manages his/her relations can help him/her to create a correct relation without tension, this results life satisfaction and success for him/her (Earley, et al. 2006).

Life Satisfaction

In a study conducted by Veenhoven (1996) he said that, like most attitudinal phenomena, life-satisfaction is only partially reflected in behavior. Some social behaviors tend to be more frequent among the satisfied (active, outgoing, friendly), such conduct can also be observed among the dissatisfied. Likewise, non-verbal behaviors such as frequent smiling or enthusiastic movements appear to be only modestly related to self-report of life-satisfaction. Consequently, estimates of someone's life satisfaction by his peers are often wrong.

The concept of life-satisfaction denotes an overall evaluation of life. So the appraisal that life is 'exciting' does not necessarily mean that it is 'satisfying'. There may be too much excitement in life, and too few other qualities. An overall evaluation of life involves all relevant criteria in the mind of the individual: for example, how good one feels, how well expectations are likely to be met and how desirable various factors are deemed to be, etc. The object of evaluation is life-as a-whole; not a specific area of life, e.g., employment. Enjoyment of work may add to the appreciation of life, but does not constitute it (Kong, et al. 2012).

Personal

Satisfaction is a state of mind. It is an evaluative appraisal of something. The term refers to both 'contentment' and 'enjoyment'. As such it covers cognitive- as well as affective-appraisals. Satisfaction can be both evanescent and stable through time. Life satisfaction is the degree to which a person positively evaluates the overall quality of his/her life as-a-whole. In other words, how much the person likes the life he/she leads (Palmer, et al., 2002). Life satisfaction is increasingly recognized as an important dimension of wellbeing. It does not only captures very immediate aspects of positive and negative life experience, but

is also linked to subsequent outcomes including differences in morbidity and mortality risks (Kong, et al., (2012)

The measurement of life satisfaction is now regarded as a legitimate policy aim as well as a source of extensive academic investigation. Life satisfaction is, therefore, an important outcome and potential source of inequalities across ethnic groups (Lewis, et al., 2011). Jiang and Hu, (2012) believed that social relation have so much effect on persons' life satisfaction. Also there is a relation between the person's happiness and work designation. Van Dyne, (2009) also believes that happiness and emotional constancy relate to cultural intelligence. So it is expected that people who have high cultural intelligence, regarding that they understand other feeling and have relations without any conflicts and struggles, so it increases their life satisfaction.

Gilman and Huebner (2006) notice that youth reporting low life satisfaction reported higher level of intrapersonal and interpersonal distress and less positive academic experiences than youth reporting higher levels of satisfaction. In this context, Diener et al. (1985) states that although there may be some agreement about the important components of the good life such as good health and successful relationship, individuals are likely to assign different weight to these components. Therefore, Pavot and Diener (1993) suggest that researchers should also assess an individual's global judgement of his or her life rather than only his or her satisfaction with specific domains.

Professional

In recent years, the positive psychology movement has called for as much focus on strength, virtue and thriving as on disease, disorder and distress. Researchers are increasingly recognizing the contribution of subjective well-being or happiness to an individual's mental and physical health. Traditional conceptualizations of mental health, which focus only on the absence of disease or symptoms, do not provide a comprehensive account of the quality of a person's life (Zulig, et al., 2006).

Positive indicators such as life satisfaction should be included in any assessment to measure overall psychological well-being. Subjective well-being as a multidimensional construct includes such cognitive and affective components as satisfaction with life, the frequent experience of positive emotions and the infrequent experience of negative emotions. Life satisfaction is often considered a desirable goal, in and of itself, stemming from the Aristotelian ethical model, eudemonism, (from eudaimonia, the Greek word for happiness) where correct actions lead to individual well - being, with happiness representing the supreme good Moreover, life satisfaction is related to better physical and mental health, longevity, and other outcomes that are considered positive in nature. Men and women are similar in their overall levels of life satisfaction although women do report more positive and negative affect. Married people are more satisfied with their lives and those with life-long marriages appear to be the most satisfied (Kong, et. al., 2012).

Jiang, (2016) emphasized that life satisfaction tends to be stable over time suggesting a dispositional, and perhaps, even a genetic component. Life satisfaction set-point (a relatively stable level that an individual will return to after facing varying life circumstances) reporting that there are longitudinal

changes in satisfaction levels for about one-quarter of their respondents. LS is related to other psychological constructs such as self-esteem but still distinct. Different correlates are found for LS and self-esteem.

Furthermore, Jiang (2016) added that gender differences are often found for self-esteem (males are typically higher) but usually not for LS. Life satisfaction is an overall assessment of feelings and attitudes about one's life at a particular point in time ranging from negative to positive. It is one of three major indicators of well-being: life satisfaction, positive affect, and negative affect. Although satisfaction with current life circumstances is often assessed in research studies, also include the following under life satisfaction: desire to change one's life; satisfaction with past; satisfaction with future; and significant other's views of one's life.

Despite extensive research with adults, there have been only a limited number of studies of LS in children and youth. Possible reasons for this neglect include a lack of well-validated, age-appropriate measures of children. It has been assumed that young children have difficulty in evaluating their global LS because they are unable to integrate evaluative information from various life domains (Raabe, et al. 2007).

Life satisfaction was viewed to have connection with emotional fluctuations (Diener and Diener, 1996), can influence changes in behavior (Lewis et al. 2011) Thus, the finding may suggest that having high satisfaction in life could reflect of having positive mental health and wellness. Nevertheless, Gilman and Huebner (2006) claim that maintaining a positive outlook of life may serve as a signal against the backdrop of ongoing cognitive appraisals, affective states and environmental circumstances. People who are happier will highly likely produce better work, have good interpersonal relationship with others and possess a healthier mental state and more endurance to stress and challenging situations. Subsequently it was found in their studies that people with high life satisfaction correlates with high academic performance, high interpersonal and intrapersonal functioning than people reporting with low life satisfaction. They also reveal that high levels of life satisfaction and various indices of positive behavioral and psychological adjustment are interrelated.

The result reveals that there is a relationship between the two variables. The result suggests that academic leadership enhances life satisfaction. There may be other factors that enhance life satisfaction among these undergraduates apart from academic achievement. Life satisfaction may be enhanced by positive relationships, family environment, peer acceptance and good health (Bradley and Corwyn 2004).

There is a significant positive correlation found between metacognitive intelligence and life satisfaction. Metacognitive strategies and intelligence regulate cognitive processes and contribute to learning. They facilitate learning. Understanding the learning processes and information utilization set the stage for the learning to occur; thus, they help the individual hold a positive feeling towards life. People may experience life satisfaction that is a stable and general feeling that reflects the attitudes people hold about the world they live in (Schimmack, 2002). Metacognitive strategies help identify the suitable strategy to do a certain task and to assess one's performance so that people may achieve their goals and enjoy life satisfaction. The present findings also revealed the multiple relations of metacognitive intelligence and life satisfaction (Mohri, et al., 2013).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The framework of this study involves the theories of Robert J. Sternberg's Triarchic Theory of Intelligence, Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, and William Glasser's Choice Theory. The Triarchic Theory of Intelligence was formulated by Robert J. Sternberg, a prominent figure in the research of human intelligence. Sternberg's definition of human intelligence is "(a) mental activity directed toward purposive adaptation to, selection and shaping of, real-world environments relevant to one's life" (Sternberg, 1985) which means that intelligence is how well an individual deals with environmental changes throughout their lifespan.

Sternberg (1986) said that Cultural Intelligence or CQ is grounded in the theory of multiple intelligences where CQ is similar to, yet distinct from, other forms of intelligence. CQ is similar to these other intelligences because it is a set of capabilities, rather than preferred ways of behaving (Mayer et al., 2000). These constructs differ, however, in the nature of the abilities. Sternberg's theory comprises three parts: componential, experiential, and practical. The experiential dimension involves the way that individuals deal with the internal and external world. This dimension looks at how individuals deal with novelty and the eventual automation of processes. Finally, the contextual dimension examines how individuals adapt to, shape, and select the external world around them.

On the other hand, Psychologist Abraham Maslow (1943, 1954) stated in his theory the Hierarchy of Needs that human motivation is based on people seeking fulfillment and change through personal growth. Self-actualized people are those who were fulfilled and doing all they were capable of. The growth of self-actualization (Maslow, 1962) refers to the need for personal growth and discovery that is present throughout a person's life.

Maslow (1962) believed self-actualization could be measured through the concept of peak experiences. This occurs when a person experiences the world totally for what it is, and there are feelings of euphoria, joy and wonder. It is important to note that self-actualization is a continual process of becoming rather than a perfect state one reaches of a 'happy ever after'. Moreover, the Choice Theory of William Glasser posits that behaviors we choose are central to our existence. Our behavior (choices) is driven by six genetically driven needs (survival needs): food, clothing, shelter, breathing, personal safety, security, and four fundamental psychological needs: belonging /connecting /love; power/ significance/ competence; freedom/ autonomy; and fun/ learning.

Choice theory states that almost all behavior is chosen, and that these are driven by genes to satisfy five basic needs: survival, love and belonging, power, freedom and fun. In practice, the most important need is love and belonging, as closeness and connectedness with the people we cared for is a requisite for satisfying all of the needs.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Enlightened by the theories discussed above, the research paradigm has been conceptualized by the researcher. These 3 theories have one thing in common, and that is each person is unique. For Maslow, the motivation for self-actualization leads people in different directions. For some people self-actualization can be achieved through creating works of art or literature, for others through sport, in the classroom, or within a corporate setting. This thought of Maslow is similar to the idea of Sternberg, 1985, “The Triarchic Theory of Intelligence”, that human intelligence is a mental activity directed toward purposive adaptation to, selection and shaping of, real-world environments relevant to one's life” which means that intelligence is how well an individual deals with environmental changes throughout lifespan. In self-actualization a person comes to find a meaning to life that is important to them. Furthermore, according to the Choice theory, the most important need is love and belonging, as closeness and connectedness with the people we care about is a requisite for satisfying all of the needs which is relative to the theory of Maslow, the Hierarchy of Needs.

The paradigm of the study depicted in Figure 1, using the Dependent – Independent Variables model. It illustrates the influence and relationship of the variables being studied. Mainly, the influence of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents to the decision-making confidence and cultural Intelligence of the respondents were determined; further, the relationship between cultural intelligence and decision-making confidence of the respondents; the influence of decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction level of the respondents were examined. In determining the above statements, the study explored the socio-demographic profile, cultural intelligence, decision-making confidence level and life satisfaction level of the respondents.

Figure 1 shows the influence of the Socio-Demographic Profile of the respondents to the Decision-making Confidence and Cultural Intelligence; the relationship of Cultural Intelligence and Decision-making Confidence; and the influence of the Decision-making Confidence and Cultural Intelligence to the Life Satisfaction of the respondents.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the research framework of the study

Null Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study made out of the mentioned problem.

1. There is no significant influence of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents on their decision-making.
2. There is no significant influence of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents on their cultural intelligence.
3. There is no significant relationship between cultural intelligence and decision-making of the school heads.
4. There is no significant influence of the decision-making to the life satisfaction of the school heads.
5. There is no significant influence of the cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction of the school heads.

METHODS

Research Design

The researcher used both the qualitative and quantitative research design which is concerned with the description of data and characteristics about a population. A descriptive-correlational research design will be utilized in the study. The goal was the acquisition of factual, accurate and systematic data that can be used in averages, frequencies and similar statistical calculations.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted to the two (2) Department of Education Divisions in Region 12: Cotabato and Kidapawan City Divisions. In line with the cityhood of Kidapawan came the birth of DepEd Kidapawan City Division, it was conceived as an interim city division on February 16, 1999 with Dr. Gloria M. Mudanza as the Schools Division Superintendent and Ma. Rosa C. Gutierrez, Assistant Schools Division Superintendent.

The present Cotabato Schools Division was created on November 22, 1973 with the creation of North Cotabato Province by virtues of Presidential Decree No. 341. The newly organized schools division became operative in the early part of January 1975 under the first SDS Felix Villarín. At present, The Division of Cotabato is composed of 42 districts throughout the Province and 79 secondary schools excluding annexes.

Figure 2. Map of the Schools involved in the study.

Sampling Procedure

Equal allocation was used in this study. Fifteen (15) private school principals or school heads from Kidapawan City and another Fifteen (15) private school principals or school heads from North Cotabato divisions were subjects in this study. Complete enumeration of their 240 teachers under these 30 school heads aided in answering the Part III and Part IV of the instruments used. Stratified Sampling Technique was used in identifying the private schools from each division.

Research Instruments

This study used the following sets of questionnaires.

1. Socio-Demographic Profile Questionnaire – It is a researcher-made questionnaire to identify the age, gender, ethnicity, years in service, educational attainment and designation of the respondents.

2. Decision-making Confidence Test – Is a modified 25-items questionnaire divided into 5 categories; Academic Leadership, Governance, Guidance and Human Resource Management, Financial and Infrastructure Management, and External Relations developed by Jane Banney. This questionnaire was validated with Cronbach’s Reliability test and gained an Alpha Value of 0.938. This test was conducted with 24 respondents or 10% of the total sample of the study.

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Very High Confidence
3.01	4.00	High Confidence
2.01	3.00	Average Confidence
1.01	2.00	Low Confidence
0.01	1.00	Very Low Confidence

3. Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) - This questionnaire is consisted of 20 questions categorized into 4 categories; Metacognitive CQ, Cognitive CQ, Motivational CQ, Behavioral CQ developed by Dr. Lynn Van Dyne of Michigan State University and Dr. Soon Ang of Nanyang Business School Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. This questionnaire was validated with Cronbach’s Reliability test and gained an Alpha Value of 0.937. This test was conducted with 24 respondents or 10% of the total sample of the study.

Scale:

4.01	5.00	very high intelligence
3.01	4.00	high intelligence
2.01	3.00	average intelligence
1.01	2.00	low intelligence
0.01	1.00	very low intelligence

4. Life Satisfaction Questionnaire – Is a modified 30-items test categorized as personal and professional aspects on life satisfaction developed by Dr. Elia Gourgouris. This questionnaire was validated with

Cronbach's Reliability test and gained an Alpha Value of 0.971. This test was conducted with 24 respondents or 10% of the total sample of the study.

Scale:	4.01	5.00	Highly Satisfactory
	3.01	4.00	Very Satisfactory
	2.01	3.00	Satisfactory
	1.01	2.00	Moderately Satisfactory
	0.01	1.00	Lowly Satisfactory

Data Gathering Procedure

Permissions were sought from the Schools Division Superintendents to administer the test to the school heads of the Department of Education Kidapawan City and Cotabato Divisions. The researcher distributed and retrieved the sets of questionnaire to and from the respondents and have a one-on-one interview with selected school heads. Table 1 below shows the activity flow of the research.

Table 1 Timetable of Activities.

ACTIVITIES	TARGET DATE
Draft Chapters 1 – 3	December 2016
Title Defense	December 9, 2016
Outline Defense	December 17, 2016
Seek permission to conduct research questionnaires	December 19, 2016
Administer research questionnaires to the respondents	December 2016 – January 2017
Gather data	January 2017
Compute gathered data results	January 2016
Draft Chapters 4 – 5	February 2016
Final Defense	February 2016
Final Paper	February-March 2016

Statistical Analysis

The weighted average or weighted mean was used to determine the school heads' socio demographic profile, cultural intelligence, decision-making confidence, and life satisfaction. It is a measure

that assigns a scale value to each of the responses, thus, the instrument yielded a total score for each respondent.

The formula is as follows:

$$WX = \frac{\text{Total weighted point}}{N}$$

Where: WX - weighted Mean

N – Total number of Responses

To determine the influence of the socio-demographic profile of the respondents to their decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence and the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence to their life satisfaction, multiple regression was used. The multiple regression is done in SPSS/WIN by selecting "Statistics" on the toolbar, followed by "Regression" and then "Linear." The interface should appear as follows: In the first analysis, Y1 is the dependent variable and two independent variables are entered in the first block, X1 and X2.

To determine the relationships between decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence, Pearson r was used. The formula is as follows:

Pearson r

$$r = \frac{N\Sigma XY - \Sigma X \Sigma Y}{\sqrt{[N\Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2][N\Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2]}}$$

Where: r = Pearson N = number of samples

X = 1st group Y = 2nd group

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents all the data that were gathered and analyzed by the researcher to answer the problems stated in Chapter 1 of this study. The results were based from the questionnaires answered by the participants of this study which show the socio-demographic profile, cultural intelligence, decision-making confidence level and life satisfaction level of the school heads.

Socio Demographic Profile of the School Heads

Table 2 presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, years in service and highest educational attainment.

Out of the 30 respondents, 13 are 41-50 years old, 9 are 51-60 years old, 3 are 31-40 years old, 3 are 61 years old above and 2 are less than 30 years old. This implies that there is a representation of each age category and that majority of the respondents are 41-50 years old. In terms of gender, there are 27 female and 7 male school heads. This clearly depicts that most of the respondents are females. The Ilonggo school heads dominated the respondents with the frequency count of 15; 9 are Cebuano; 4 are Ilokano; 1 is Boholano; and 1 is Tagalog which depicts that in terms of ethnicity, the respondents are ethnically diverse.

In their years of service, there are 14 school heads who have rendered 14 to 20 years in service; 6 have 21 to 27 years in service; 3 have less than 6 years in service; 3 have 28 to 34 years in service; 2 have 7 to 13 years in service; and 2 have 35 years and above years of service. This implies that the respondents have different length of services rendered to their respective institution. The highest educational attainment that the school heads have is Master's degree having a frequency count of 15; 11 have Bachelor's Degrees, and 4 have Doctoral Degrees. This discloses that the majority of the respondents have sought for post baccalaureate degrees and studies which imply that the respondents have continuing education as part of their professional development.

Generally, the school heads are mostly female, aged between 41-50, have Master's degrees with 14-20 years of service.

Table 2 The Socio-demographic profile of the school heads

Profile	Frequency, (N = 30)	Percentage, (%)
Age:		
Less than 30 years old	2	6.67
31 - 40	3	10.00
41 – 50	13	43.33
51 – 60	9	30.00
61 years above	3	10.00
Gender:		
Male	7	23.33
Female	27	76.67
Ethnicity:		
Cebuano	9	30.00
Boholano	1	3.33
Ilonggo	15	50.00
Tagalog	1	3.33
Ilocano	4	13.33
Years in Service:		
Less than 6 years	3	10.00
7 – 13 years	2	6.67
14 – 20 years	14	46.67
21 – 27 years	6	20.00
28 – 34 years	3	10.00
35 years above	2	6.67
Highest Educ. Attainment:		
Bachelor	11	36.67
Masters	15	50.00
Doctoral	4	13.33

Confidence Level in Decision-making

The level of confidence in decision-making of the school heads in terms of academic leadership, governance, guidance and human resource management, financial and infrastructure management and external relations is discussed in the following paragraphs.

Academic Leadership

The school heads have very high confidence in decision-making in terms of Academic Leadership (Table 3). This means that the school heads have very high regards for academic leadership through pursuing excellence in teaching and learning and in research; thus, promote collaboration with other schools and represent the interests and needs of the school to the external community to maintain personal academic standing, including the pursuit of research and scholarship.

The data revealed that, although, the school heads have very high confidence level of decision-making confidence in academic leadership, they give lesser attention in representing the interests and needs of the school through membership of the teachers' organizations. One interviewed school head said that there are only few teachers' organization in this division which are active organizations; some of it are the Cotabato Private Schools Association (COPRISA) for Cotabato Division and Kidapawan Private Schools Association (KIPRISA) for Kidapawan City Division. This implies that school heads are not very particular in representing the interest and needs of the school through membership of the teacher's organization other than the organizations mentioned above. This may limit their full potentials as academic leaders and might curtail the development of their leadership skills.

Table 3 Decision-making confidence of school heads in terms of academic leadership.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 Promoting collaboration with other schools.	4.12	Very High confidence
2 Encouraging the pursuit of excellence in teaching and learning and in research.	4.22	Very High confidence
3 Representing the interests and needs of the School and to the external community.	4.21	Very High confidence
4 Maintaining personal academic standing, including the pursuit of research and scholarship.	4.12	Very High confidence
5 Representing the interests and needs of the school through membership of the teachers' organizations.	4.09	Very High confidence
Weighted Mean	4.15	Very High confidence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Very High Confidence
3.01	4.00	High Confidence
2.01	3.00	Average Confidence
1.01	2.00	Low Confidence

0.01 1.00 Very Low Confidence

Governance

The school heads have very high confidence in decision-making in terms of governance which means that the school heads develop and maintain the strategic and academic planning functions including the setting of goals and targets of the school; and develop and maintain quality assurance processes, particularly in relation to teaching, research and the supervision of students.

The results show that the school heads give lesser importance in establishing and maintaining suitable organizational and committee structure. This implies that private schools have different organizational structure compared to the public schools. Some schools call their heads as academic head, director, administrator, and head master which pertains to the same functions like the public school principals.

This is probably because there is no prototype organizational and committee structure set by the government for private schools, hence, they are given the freedom of their organizational and committee structure as long as the minimum requirements set by the government to manage and administer a school are fully satisfied. In an interview with a supervisor, he states that there is no specific educational law that limits or hinders a private school in establishing and maintaining an organizational structure.

Table 4 Decision-making confidence of school heads in terms of governance.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 Establishing and maintaining a suitable organizational and committee structure.	4.19	Very high confidence
2 Consulting with relevant committees and staff on the implementation of the school policies.	4.30	Very high confidence
3 Developing and maintaining the strategic and academic planning functions including the setting of goals and targets of the school.	4.28	Very high confidence
4 Developing and maintaining quality assurance processes, particularly in relation to teaching, research and the supervision of students.	4.30	Very high confidence
5 Allocating duties to teachers in an equitable manner to ensure the effective and efficient performance of the teaching, research and service functions.	4.24	Very high confidence
Weighted Mean	4.26	Very high confidence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Very High Confidence
3.01	4.00	High Confidence
2.01	3.00	Average Confidence

1.01 2.00 Low Confidence
 0.01 1.00 Very Low Confidence

Guidance and Human Resource Management

There is a very high confidence level in terms of Guidance and Human Resource Management of the decision-making confidence of the school heads is shown in Table 5 which implies that they comply with the school policies and guidelines; support professional development of teachers, establish mechanisms to ensure that equity, ensure health and safety policies, and manage the recruitment and selection of teachers.

However, they give lesser emphasis on appraising teachers' performance and management of issues and grievances as compared to the other Guidance and Human Resource Management indicators. This might be one of the many reasons, aside from financial security, why some teachers leave the private school and transfer to public school, because performance appraisal and management of issues and grievances of teachers are not given more serious emphasis by some school heads.

Table 5 Decision-making confidence of school heads in terms of guidance and human resource management.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 Complying with the school policies and guidelines.	4.38	Very high confidence
2 Supporting professional development of teachers.	4.31	Very high confidence
3 Managing the recruitment and selection of teachers.	4.27	Very high confidence
4 Appraising teachers' performance and management of issues and grievances.	4.17	Very high confidence
5 Establishing mechanisms to ensure that equity and workplace health and safety policies are observed.	4.28	Very high confidence
Weighted Mean	4.28	Very high confidence

Scale:

4.01 5.00 Very High Confidence
 3.01 4.00 High Confidence
 2.01 3.00 Average Confidence
 1.01 2.00 Low Confidence
 0.01 1.00 Very Low Confidence

Financial and Infrastructure Management

The decision-making of the school heads in terms financial and infrastructure management is very high confidence level, (Table 6). This implies that the school heads have develop links and partnerships with stakeholders; monitor expenditure and allocations; increase revenue by attracting students; and develop and maintain the school area and infrastructure resources.

Although the respondents got a very high confidence level, the data in Table 6 reveal that lesser attention is given by the school heads in managing finances including budgeting and planning for equipment and other infrastructure expenditure as compared to the other financial infrastructure management indicators.

This is an indication that some private schools, most probably the small ones, have financial issues because they depend merely on the tuition fees of the students and the budget allotted for equipment and infrastructure development depends on the number of students enrolled in the school.

Table 6 Decision-making confidence of school heads in terms of financial and infrastructure management.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 Monitoring expenditure and allocations.	4.22	Very high confidence
2 Developing links and partnerships with stakeholders.	4.26	Very high confidence
3 Pursuing opportunities to increase revenue by attracting students.	4.18	Very high confidence
4 Managing and maintaining the school area and infrastructure resources.	4.15	Very high confidence
5 Managing finances including budgeting and planning for equipment and other infrastructure expenditure.	4.11	Very high confidence
Weighted Mean	4.16	Very high confidence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Very High Confidence
3.01	4.00	High Confidence
2.01	3.00	Average Confidence
1.01	2.00	Low Confidence
0.01	1.00	Very Low Confidence

External Relation

Table 7 discloses a very high confidence level on the decision-making of the school heads in terms external relations which indicates that the school heads have links to follow-up performance of learners, links with government departments and authorities, links with graduates and alumni, and links with other networks. Even though they have very high confidence in decision-making in terms of external relations

they provide lesser attention in contacting business, commerce and industry organizations relevant to the school's research and develop research partnerships.

This result denotes that the links to other business, industry and organization which pertains to research and to develop research partnerships is the weakest portion for private school heads in the two divisions. This is probably because research isn't really a priority to some private schools unlike the public schools where teachers are required to conduct action researches.

Most of the teachers in private schools are neophyte teachers who are getting some years of experiences then transfer later on to public schools to have financial stability. This could be a possible reason why school heads do not invest and show much attention in research and develop research partnerships. Another possible factor is that school heads might be hesitant to look for opportunities for research and partnership with other entities because of it is expensive to conduct researches and that resources of private schools are limited and reliant to their students.

Table 7 Level of confidence in decision-making of school heads in terms of external relation.

Statement	Mean	Description
21 Maintaining effective links with graduates and alumni.	4.08	Very high confidence
22 Maintaining links to follow-up performance of learners.	4.21	Very high confidence
23 Setting up and maintaining productive links with networks.	4.04	Very high confidence
24 Maintaining effective links with government departments and authorities.	4.09	Very high confidence
25 Contacting business, commerce and industry organizations relevant to the School's research and develop research partnerships.	3.90	high confidence
Weighted Mean	4.07	Very high confidence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Very High Confidence
3.01	4.00	High Confidence
2.01	3.00	Average Confidence
1.01	2.00	Low Confidence
0.01	1.00	Very Low Confidence

Cultural Intelligence (CQ) of the School Heads

This part of the study discusses the cultural intelligence (CQ) of the school heads in terms of Metacognitive Intelligence, Cognitive Intelligence, Motivational Intelligence and Behavioral Intelligence.

Metacognitive CQ

A very high intelligence is the overall result in the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of metacognitive CQ, (Table 8), which denotes that the school heads are conscious of the cultural knowledge when interacting with people with different cultural backgrounds. It implies that the school heads adjust their cultural knowledge as they interact with people from a culture that is unfamiliar to them.

However, the result shows that they give lesser consciousness of the rules for expressing non-verbal behaviors in other cultures as compared to the other metacognitive intelligence indicators. This implies that the school heads do not have very high intelligence being conscious of the rules in expressing non-verbal behaviors by which other cultural groups might misinterpret or misunderstood. These non-verbal behaviors refer to actuations of school heads when interacting to other people. There are actions that believed to be positive to their understanding but it might be negative to other cultures. One of these is the raising of an eyebrow to affirm a statement. Others might understand it as affirmation or a sign of disagreement or disbelief.

Table 8 Cultural intelligence of school heads in terms of metacognitive CQ.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 He/She is conscious of the cultural knowledge he/she use when interacting with people with different cultural backgrounds.	4.30	Very High Intelligence
2 He/She can adjust my cultural knowledge as he/she interact with people from a culture that is unfamiliar to me.	4.23	Very High Intelligence
3 He/She is conscious of the cultural knowledge he/she apply to cross-cultural interactions.	4.20	Very High Intelligence
4 He/She check the accuracy of my cultural knowledge as he/she interact with people from different cultures.	4.13	Very High Intelligence
5 He/She is conscious of the rules for expressing non-verbal behaviors in other cultures.	3.93	High Intelligence
Weighted Mean	4.16	Very High Intelligence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	very high intelligence
3.01	4.00	high intelligence
2.01	3.00	average intelligence
1.01	2.00	low intelligence
0.01	1.00	very low intelligence

Cognitive CQ

As indicated in the result in Table 9 that the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of cognitive CQ is high intelligence which depicts that the respondents know the arts and crafts, cultural values, religious beliefs, legal and economic systems of other cultures. However, they show moderate intelligence in terms of their cognitive intelligence on the marriage systems of other culture and give lesser consciousness of the rules on vocabulary and grammar of other languages / dialects. This is an implication that the school heads are not exposed to other cultural groups when it comes to the marriage systems and dialects. The school heads are not highly intelligent of the grammar rules and vocabulary of other cultures because they do not use the language or dialect as their mother tongue. Some private school use English as their medium of conversation in the campus. Using a different dialect aside from English and Filipino as means of communication is prohibited to some schools. It might be difficult for them to learn the other dialects since it may not be applicable to their position.

Table 9 Cultural intelligence of school heads in terms of cognitive CQ.

Statement	Mean	Description
6 He/She knows the legal and economic systems of other cultures.	3.67	High Intelligence
7 He/She knows the rules (e.g., vocabulary, grammar) of other languages / dialects.	3.43	High Intelligence
8 He/She knows the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures.	3.73	High Intelligence
9 He/She knows the marriage systems of other cultures.	3.47	High Intelligence
10 He/She knows the arts and crafts of other cultures.	3.80	High Intelligence
Weighted Mean	3.62	High Intelligence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	very high intelligence
3.01	4.00	high intelligence
2.01	3.00	average intelligence
1.01	2.00	low intelligence
0.01	1.00	very low intelligence

Motivational CQ

It is revealed in Table 10 that the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of motivational CQ is high intelligence. It implies that even if they enjoy interacting with people; they are confident that they can socialize with locals in a different culture; they can deal with the stress of adjusting to a culture

that is new to them; and they are confident that they can get accustomed to the conditions in a different culture; they might prefer not enjoy to live with cultures that are unfamiliar to them. This means that the school heads can adjust to the different cultural conditions new to them but might give lesser appreciation to live in culture they are not used to.

Table 10 Cultural intelligence of school heads in terms of motivational CQ.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 He/She enjoys interacting with people from different cultures.	4.47	Very High Intelligence
2 He/She is confident that he/she can socialize with locals in a culture that is unfamiliar to him/her.	4.03	Very High Intelligence
3 He/She is sure he/she can deal with the stress of adjusting to a culture that is new to him/her.	3.90	High Intelligence
4 He/She enjoys living in cultures that are unfamiliar to him/her.	3.63	High Intelligence
5 He/She is confident that he/she can get accustomed to the conditions in a different culture.	3.90	High Intelligence
Weighted Mean	3.99	High Intelligence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	very high intelligence
3.01	4.00	high intelligence
2.01	3.00	average intelligence
1.01	2.00	low intelligence
0.01	1.00	very low intelligence

Behavioral CQ

The cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of behavioral Intelligence is high intelligence which indicates that they pause and silence differently to suit different cross-cultural situations; change their verbal behavior such as accent and tone; vary the rate as they speak and change their non-verbal behavior when a cross-cultural situation requires it. However, they give lesser consciousness altering their facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.

Table 11 Cultural intelligence of school heads in terms of behavioral CQ.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 He/She change his/her verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.	4.00	Very High Intelligence
2 He/She uses pause and silence differently to suit different cross-cultural situations.	4.07	Very High Intelligence
3 He/She varies the rate of his/her speaking when a cross-cultural situation requires it.	4.00	Very High Intelligence
4 He/She changes my non-verbal behavior when a cross-cultural situation requires it.	4.00	Very High Intelligence
5 He/She alters his/her facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it.	3.90	High Intelligence
Weighted Mean	3.99	High Intelligence

Scale:

4.01	5.00	very high intelligence
3.01	4.00	high intelligence
2.01	3.00	average intelligence
1.01	2.00	low intelligence
0.01	1.00	very low intelligence

Life Satisfaction Level of the School Heads

The level of life satisfaction of school heads in terms of personal and professional aspects is presented in the following paragraphs.

Personal

Table 12 reveals that the life satisfaction level of the school heads in terms of their personal aspect is highly satisfactory. It shows that the school heads are highly satisfied to the relationship with their creator and neighbors; their intelligence, and their personal achievements.

In addition, they are also highly satisfied with their relationships with friends, family, material things, personal decisions, social standing, acts of service, financial status, health, leadership, humor and wit. The result implies that due to the busy schedules and responsibilities of the school heads in their personal life such as responsibilities at home such as taking care of their children, families, doing household chores, and other personal matters they give lesser time to satisfy their physical body with rest.

Table 12 Life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of personal.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 My personal decisions	4.38	Highly Satisfactory
2 My acts of service	4.36	Highly Satisfactory
3 My rest	4.11	Highly Satisfactory
4 My intelligence	4.52	Highly Satisfactory
5 My relationship with his/her Creator	4.66	Highly Satisfactory
6 My relationships with friends	4.46	Highly Satisfactory
7 My material things	4.38	Highly Satisfactory
8 My relationships with neighbors	4.52	Highly Satisfactory
9 My financial status	4.30	Highly Satisfactory
10 My social standing	4.38	Highly Satisfactory
11 My family relationship	4.38	Highly Satisfactory
12 My personal achievements	4.54	Highly Satisfactory
13 My humor and wit	4.16	Highly Satisfactory
14 My leadership	4.20	Highly Satisfactory
15 My health	4.23	Highly Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	4.37	Highly Satisfactory

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Highly Satisfactory
3.01	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.01	3.00	Satisfactory
1.01	2.00	Moderately Satisfactory
0.01	1.00	Lowly Satisfactory

Professional

Generally, the life satisfaction level of the school heads in terms of their professional aspect is highly satisfactory which implies that the respondents are highly satisfied with their career aspirations, work ethics, excitement to work, skills and talents, performance, work relations with subordinates, sensitivity to others and their own points of views.

Moreover, the data further reveal a highly satisfactory result of the respondents' professional life satisfaction to their commitment to the teaching profession, work attitudes, and duties and responsibilities. This means that the respondents show high regard for the teaching profession and that they feel highly satisfied with their chosen career path.

Table 13 Life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of professional.

Statement	Mean	Description
1 My work ethics	4.48	Highly Satisfactory
2 My passion and joy	4.41	Highly Satisfactory
3 My performance	4.32	Highly Satisfactory
4 My excitement to work	4.38	Highly Satisfactory
5 My work attitude	4.53	Highly Satisfactory
6 My duties and responsibilities	4.51	Highly Satisfactory
7 My work relations with subordinates	4.32	Highly Satisfactory
8 My manner of overcoming work related stress	4.41	Highly Satisfactory
9 My integrity and honesty	4.47	Highly Satisfactory
10 My commitment to the profession	4.62	Highly Satisfactory
11 My career aspirations	4.49	Highly Satisfactory
12 My control over the work-related disappointments	4.41	Highly Satisfactory
13 My skills and talents.	4.36	Highly Satisfactory
14 My points of view	4.29	Highly Satisfactory
15 My sensitivity to others	4.31	Highly Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	4.42	Highly Satisfactory

Scale:

4.01	5.00	Highly Satisfactory
3.01	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.01	3.00	Satisfactory
1.01	2.00	Moderately Satisfactory
0.01	1.00	Lowly Satisfactory

Socio – demographic Profile and Decision-making Confidence of School Heads

The following statements show the influence of the Socio-Demographic Profile of the respondents to the Decision-making Confidence Level in terms of the Academic Leadership, Governance, Guidance and Human Resource Management, Financial and Infrastructure Management and External Factors.

Socio – demographic Profile and Academic Leadership

In Table 14, the result reveals that the socio – economic profile of school heads significantly influence their decision-making confidence in terms of academic leadership (F – value = 1.808, Probability = 0.042*). The hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance.

The 17.60% of the variation of the decision-making confidence of the school heads in terms of academic leadership was accounted by their socio – demographic profile. Apparently, the remaining 82.40% was accounted by some profile not included in the context of the study.

Among the indicators used in the socio-demographic profile, gender and highest educational attainment were found to be best predictors of decision-making confidence in leading the organization of the respondents. It implies that the higher the educational attainment of the male school heads, the more confident he is in leading the organization by encouraging the pursuit of excellence in teaching and learning.

The result is consistent to a literature that although more boys are enrolled at primary and secondary education, more women are educated at tertiary level. However, for countries such as India, Pakistan, and Nigeria, women are enrolled at lower rates in tertiary education (UNESCO, 2012). This specifies that more female are educated than male. However, in the study conducted by Bengtsson, et al., (2005) it conversely indicated that men can be characterized as more confident than women especially regarding decisions. Apparently, it could also be consistent to what Hora, (2014) showed in a study that if favorable conditions are set at place and women are provided the position to lead, they are as effective and successful as more than that of their male counterparts.

Interestingly, the gender does not seem to be a determinant since the study of Gneezy, et al. (2009) stated an opposite finding that women were greater risk takers, more competitive and good decision makers.

Table 14 Socio – demographic profile and the decision-making confidence in terms of academic leadership.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	4.708	0.604	7.796	0.000
Age	0.001	0.013	0.107	0.916
Gender	-0.413	0.245	-1.686	0.045*
Ethnicity	0.015	0.091	0.165	0.870
Year in service	0.008	0.017	0.491	0.628
Highest educ'l attainment	-0.258	0.166	-1.555	0.043*

R² = 0.176

F – Value = 1.808

Probability = 0.042*

* = Significant at 5% level

Socio – demographic Profile and Governance

The result in Table 15 shows that the socio – demographic profile of school heads did not significantly influence their decision-making confidence in terms of governance (F – value = 0.339, Probability = 0.884^{ns}). Since the value of probability is significantly higher than 0.050 level of significance, the hypothesis of the study was accepted.

This implies that the age, gender, ethnicity, years in service, and highest educational attainment of the respondents do not matter and do not influence the decision-making confidence of the school heads in terms of governance.

In contrary to the result of this study, Acharya et. al (2010) reported that age, gender and highest educational attainment are factors in decision-making that women’s autonomy in decision-making is positively associated with their age and that women’s increased education is positively associated with autonomy in decision-making.

In a study conducted by Groyberg (2013), it came out that women are shown to have positive effects that improve corporate performance. In addition, having at least one woman on the board decreases bankruptcy which is supported by a study conducted by Groyberg (2013) that women are shown to have positive effects that improve corporate performance. Thus, gender is a factor in governance,

Table 15 Socio – demographic profile on the decision-making confidence in terms of governance.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	4.575	0.640	7.145	0.000
Age	-0.006	0.013	-0.460	0.649
Gender	-0.115	0.260	-0.443	0.662
Ethnicity	0.028	0.096	0.294	0.771
Year in service	0.014	0.018	0.762	0.454
Highest educ’l attainment	-0.100	0.176	-0.569	0.575

R² = 0.066

F – Value = 0.339

Probability = 0.884^{ns}

^{ns} = Not Significant

Socio – demographic Profile and Guidance and Human Resource Management

The result revealed in table 16 shows that the socio – demographic profile of school heads significantly influence their decision-making confidence in terms of guidance and human resource

management (F – value = 1.255, Probability = 0.050*). This result made to the rejection of the stated hypothesis of the study since the value of probability is equal to 0.050 level of significance.

The variation of the decision-making confidence of the school heads in terms of Guidance and Human Resource Management that was accounted by their socio – demographic profile was 17.00%. Thus, the remaining 83.00% was accounted by some indicators excluded in the context of the study.

Among the indicators, it is observed that age was found to be the best predictor of decision-making confidence in terms of guidance and human resource management of the respondents. It implies that the younger school heads are highly confident in decision-making in terms of guidance and human resource management particularly in complying with the school policies and guidelines.

The results confirms the findings of Jiang, et al., (2016) that, although, the older generations were the very first to come into leadership, the younger generations can create a more sustainable development towards management, thus, younger generations will face a different set of challenges versus the older generations and that according to Worthy (2011) although older adults, who have a vast reserve of decision-making experience to draw upon, they often perform worse, and rarely perform better than younger adults in decision-making tasks.

An alternative reason maybe because according to Scutti (2013), the ability to make rational choices changes with age that older adults were not making too cautious choices, as is traditionally assumed. In fact, the choices of elders might be seen as much too risky.

Table 16 Socio – demographic profile and the decision-making confidence in terms of guidance and human resource management.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	5.199	0.610	8.517	0.000
Age	-0.015	0.013	-1.210	0.048*
Gender	-0.245	0.247	-0.988	0.333
Ethnicity	-0.013	0.092	-0.143	0.888
Year in service	0.009	0.017	0.518	0.609
Highest educ'l attainment	-0.051	0.168	-0.306	0.762

R² = 0.170

F – Value = 1.255

Probability = 0.050*

* = Significant at 5% level

Age was found to be the best predictor of decision-making confidence in terms of external relations of the respondents. It implies that younger school heads are highly confident in decision-making in terms of external relations particularly in maintaining links to follow-up performance of learners. Subsequent study have found contrary result (Taylor, 2016), which reveals that age was found to influence performance more than did prior decision-making experience. Little evidence was found to support that older managers are less shallow decision makers.

Table 18 Socio-demographic profile and the decision-making confidence in terms of external relation.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	5.354	0.678	7.900	0.000
Age	-0.022	0.014	-1.564	0.041*
Gender	0.025	0.275	0.092	0.927
Ethnicity	0.001	0.102	0.015	0.988
Year in service	0.008	0.019	0.417	0.680
Highest educ'l attainment	-0.133	0.186	-0.712	0.483

R² = 0.157
 Probability = 0.049*

F – Value = 1.989
 * = Significant at 5% level

Socio – demographic Profile and Cultural Intelligence of the School Heads

The influence of socio-demographic profile of the respondents to the cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive, cognitive, motivational and behavioral intelligences is presented in the succeeding statements.

Socio – demographic Profile and Metacognitive CQ

It is indicated in Table 19 that the socio – demographic profile of school heads significantly influenced their cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive intelligence (F – value = 2.159, Probability = 0.043*). The hypothesis in this item was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050. At about 31.00% of the variation of the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of metacognitive intelligence was accounted by their socio – demographic profile and the remaining 69.00% was accounted by some factors excluded in the context of this study.

Apparently, the years in service was found to be the best predictor of cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive intelligence of the respondents. The result implies that the school heads who have rendered 7 to 13 and 35 years and above years of service years of service are more culturally intelligent in terms of

metacognitive intelligence. It implies that they are conscious of the cultural knowledge they use when interacting with people with different cultural backgrounds.

While it is true that older school heads are more experienced and learned than the younger ones in leading an institution, the results affirmed that the older school heads have high metacognitive intelligence. The experienced school heads may be more energetic to interact with people around them, as a result, there will be more collaboration and partnership with other cultural groups which may lead them to become more exposed to opportunities and further develop their metacognitive intelligence as school heads.

The result of this study on this concern agrees to what Earley and Ang, (2003) affirm that those with high Cultural Intelligence will have more effective performance and adjustment in multicultural work groups. However, school heads with fewer years in service have the chance of improving their metacognitive intelligence since CQ can be learned. This claim is supported by Chen, et al. (2000) that Cultural Intelligence is malleable and can be enhanced through experiences, education and training.

Moreover, Van Dyne, et al., (2010), affirmed that an individual's Cultural Intelligence depends on several factors and can be enhanced in many ways. It can change based on a person's interactions with other cultures, their effort and interest in learning about new cultures, as well as through international experiences. Awareness of other cultures can be gathered through educational, personal and work experiences.

Table 19 Socio-demographic profile and the cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive CQ.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	4.981	0.739	6.740	0.000
Age	-0.011	0.015	-0.718	0.480
Gender	-0.356	0.300	-1.187	0.247
Ethnicity	0.193	0.111	1.745	0.094
Year in service	-0.039	0.021	-1.894	0.050*
Highest educ'l attainment	0.150	0.203	0.737	0.468

R² = 0.310
 Probability = 0.043*

F - Value = 2.159
 * = Significant at 5% level

Socio – demographic Profile and Cognitive CQ

Table 20 reveals that socio – demographic profile of the school heads do not significantly influence their cultural intelligence in terms of cognitive CQ (F – value = 0.773, Probability = 0.579^{ns}). The probability value exceeds to the 0.050 level of significance, therefore, the hypothesis of the study was

accepted. Conversely, a variation of 13.90% was accounted by their socio – demographic profile while the remaining 86.10% was accounted by some indicators excluded in the context of the study.

It was considered that the years in service was a significant predictor of the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of cognitive CQ. However, a negative significance was observed. It implies that those school heads with 7 to13 and 35 years and above years in service have higher cultural cognitive intelligence than the rest which means that they know the arts and crafts, values, religious beliefs, and economic systems of other cultures. This school heads with longer years in service might have been the product of the various advocacies on cultural awareness and equality.

Experience matters, but more is not always better. A study conducted by Ladd, (2008) deviated the result of this study, that the impact of experience is strongest during the first few years of teaching; after that, marginal returns diminish. A number of studies confirm findings from existing research that, on average, brand new teachers are less effective than those with some experience under their belts.

However, the differential attrition of teachers with different levels of effectiveness may confound findings about the effects of teacher experience. While some evidence suggests that teachers who remain teaching after three years are less effective on average than those who leave, other research has found that less effective teachers are more likely to transfer and leave teaching (Harris and Sass, 2007).

Table 20 Socio–demographic profile and the cultural intelligence in terms of cognitive CQ.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	3.573	0.690	5.177	0.000
Age	0.008	0.014	0.537	0.596
Gender	-0.118	0.280	-0.420	0.678
Ethnicity	0.082	0.104	0.796	0.434
Year in Service	-0.035	0.019	-1.817	0.042*
Highest educ'l attainment	0.133	0.190	0.698	0.492

R² = 0.139
 Probability = 0.579^{ns}

F – Value = 0.773
^{ns} = Not Significant

Socio – demographic Profiles and Motivational CQ

Table 21 reveals that socio – demographic profile of the school heads do not significantly influence their cultural intelligence in terms of motivational intelligence (F – value = 0.680, Probability = 0.643^{ns}). The result leads to the acceptance of the hypothesis since the probability value is greater than 0.050 level of significance. Conversely, 12.40% of the variation of the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of motivational intelligence was accounted by their socio – demographic profile. The remaining 88.60% was accounted by some profile not included in the context of the study.

However, it was found out that the gender was considered significant predictor of the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of motivational Intelligence. It implies that the male school heads have high motivational intelligence compared to female school heads which indicates that males enjoy interacting with people from different cultures. Probably, female school heads are tied up with their home responsibilities that they don't have enough time to get acquainted with people from other cultures. Kanfer and Heggstad, (1997), states that motivational CQ reflects the capability to direct attention and energy toward learning about and functioning in situations characterized by cultural differences.

Yap, (2011) affirmed that women spent three times as long on domestic chores, such as cooking, cleaning and washing, as their husbands or partners. Some female breadwinners, however, have to shoulder the burden of all the housework as almost one in five men admitted to doing nothing at all around the home. This makes women exhausted and fewer time if not no time at all collaborating with other people from different culture. While according to Croson and Gneezy, (2009) men today do a higher share of chores and household work than any generation of men before them. Yet working women, especially working mothers, continue to do significantly more.

Table 21 Socio-demographic profile and the cultural intelligence in terms of motivational CQ.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	4.582	0.759	6.035	0.000
Age	0.000	0.016	-0.013	0.990
Gender	-0.447	0.308	-1.451	0.046*
Ethnicity	0.026	0.114	0.224	0.825
Year in service	-0.019	0.021	-0.888	0.383
Highest educ. attainment	0.037	0.209	0.177	0.861

R² = 0.124
 Probability = 0.643^{ns}

F - Value = 0.680

^{ns} = Not Significant

Socio – demographic Profiles and Behavioral CQ

As indicated in Table 22, there is a significant influence in the socio-demographic profile of the school heads to their cultural intelligence in terms of behavioral intelligence (F – value = 1.544, Probability = 0.044*) therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance.

Moreover, 24.30% of the variation of the cultural intelligence of the school heads in terms of behavioral intelligence was accounted by their socio – demographic profile. The remaining 75.70% was accounted by some profile not included in the context of the study. It is established that gender is the best predictor of cultural intelligence in terms of behavioral intelligence of the respondents. It implies that the

male school heads have high behavioral intelligence than female which means that males pause and silence differently to suit different cross-cultural situations. One evident characteristic of men is to be silent in a situation specially when they are not used to it or they do not know how to react. This is probably the reason why men behave differently when there is a cross-cultural situation. They pause and think before expressing their thoughts.

An affirmation to this statement is given by Brislin et al. (2006) that those with high cognitive intelligence (CQ) understand similarities and differences across cultures. Van Dyne and Ang, (2009) declared that people with higher CQs are regarded as better able to successfully blend into any environment, using more effective business practices, than those with a lower CQ.

However, women, on the other hand, can equally do the same since cultural Intelligence (CQ) sees no gender because it is believed to be the person’s capability to function effectively in situations characterized by cultural diversity (Earley and Mosakowski, 2005). As Cultural Intelligence (CQ) is a specific form of intelligence focused on capabilities to grasp, reason and behave effectively in situations characterized by cultural diversity (Schmidt and Hunters, 2000).

Table 22 Socio–demographic profile and the cultural intelligence in terms of behavioral CQ.

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	5.279	0.760	6.947	0.000
Age	-0.015	0.016	-0.956	0.348
Gender	-0.452	0.308	-1.467	0.045*
Ethnicity	0.092	0.114	0.803	0.430
Year in service	-0.023	0.021	-1.071	0.295
Highest educ. attainment	0.011	0.209	0.055	0.957

R² = 0.243
 Probability = 0.044*

F – Value = 1.544
 * = Significant at 5% level

Decision-making Confidence and Cultural Intelligence

Table 23 shows the degree of relationship between the decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence of the school heads. It is found out that there is no significant degree of relationship observed between decision-making confidence in terms of academic leadership, governance, guidance and human resource management, financial and infrastructure management, and cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive CQ, cognitive CQ motivational CQ and behavioral CQ of the school heads.

Nevertheless, significant degree of relationships are observed between the external relations on decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence in terms of motivational CQ and behavioral CQ of

the school heads. Therefore, the null hypothesis of the study is rejected. A negative significance is reflected by the correlation coefficient of motivation CQ (-0.370*) and Behavioral CQ (-0.378*) which indicates a moderately small negative correlation between the two variables. This implies that when the behavioral and motivational intelligence of the school heads go down, there is a reason to believe that the decision-making confidence in terms of external relations might go up or vice versa. However, the relationship of the two variables does not necessarily mean that one is the cause or the effect of the other variable. It does not imply cause and effect relationship (Punzalan and Eduarte, 2008).

Further, this implies that when the school heads have high confidence in maintaining links to learners' performance, alumni, networks, government authorities, business, commerce and industry their motivational intelligence in interacting, socializing, and adjusting with people from other culture, their behavioral intelligence such as changing their accent, tone, rate of speaking, non-behavioral and facial expressions to adjust from cross-cultural situations might moderately drop down or vice versa.

This relationship concurs with the concept developed by Groves and Feyerherm, (2011) that without the insights offered by cultural intelligence, employees are at a disadvantage when making strategic decisions, particularly in the midst of a crisis. Moreover, Cultural intelligence helps people understand the perspectives and priorities of others and work cooperatively to develop mutually acceptable decisions, Janssens and Brett (2006). The confirmation made by Earley, et al., (2006) that decisions are based on the beliefs, cultural intelligence, values and previous experiences of individuals. In contrary to the result that there is no significant relationship between Metacognitive CQ and Cognitive CQ to the Decision-making confidence of the school heads. Groves and Feyerherm, (2011) said that with high CQ—especially CQ Knowledge (Cognitive) and CQ Strategy (metacognitive) — people can diagnose situations from multiple perspectives and make effective decisions in culturally diverse contexts.

Table 23 Relationship between the decision-making confidence and the cultural intelligence (CQ).

		Metacog- nitive	Cognitive	Motivational	Behavioral
Academic Leadership	Pearson r	0.005	-0.059	-0.058	-0.173
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.980	0.757	0.761	0.361
	N	30	30	30	30
Governance	Pearson r	-0.094	-0.100	-0.041	-0.225
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.620	0.599	0.828	0.233
	N	30	30	30	30
Guidance and Human Resource Management	Pearson r	0.170	0.157	0.066	0.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.369	0.407	0.728	0.772
	N	30	30	30	30
Financial and Infrastructure Management	Pearson r	0.010	-0.009	-0.164	-0.071
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.956	0.962	0.385	0.711
	N	30	30	30	30

External Relations	Pearson r	-0.247	-0.072	-0.370*	-0.378*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.189	0.705	0.044	0.040
	N	30	30	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Decision-making Confidence and Life Satisfaction

The influence of decision-making confidence to the life satisfaction of the respondents in terms of personal and professional aspect is presented in the succeeding statements.

Decision-making and Personal Life Satisfaction

Table 24 indicates that there is a significant influence in the decision-making confidence of the school heads to their personal life satisfaction (F – value = 59.974, Probability = 0.000**) therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance. The 56.20% of the variation of the life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of personal life satisfaction was accounted by their decision-making confidence. The remaining 43.80% was accounted by some aspects not included in the context of the study.

It is established that Academic Leadership, Guidance and Human Resource Management and External Relations are the best predictor of the personal life satisfaction of the respondents. It implies that school heads with very high confidence in decision-making in terms of academic leadership, guidance and human resource management and external relations have highly satisfactory personal life. This result affirms the statement of Malik, et al., (2013) that academic leadership enhances life satisfaction. Conversely, the study of Gilman and Huebner (2006) proposed that people who are happier will highly likely produce better work, have good interpersonal relationship with others and possess a healthier mental state and more endurance to stress and challenging situations.

Table 24 Decision-making confidence and personal life satisfaction

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	1.341	0.179	7.483	0.000
Academic leadership	0.235	0.065	3.606	0.000**
Governance	-0.016	0.072	-0.219	0.827
Guidance and HRM	0.303	0.066	4.565	0.000**
Financial and Infra. Mgt.	0.073	0.062	1.165	0.245
External Relations	0.128	0.060	2.140	0.033*

R² = 0.562
 Probability = 0.000**

F – Value = 59.974
 ** = Significant at 1% level

* = Significant at 5% level

Decision-making and Professional Life Satisfaction

Table 25 reveals that there is a significant influence in the decision-making confidence of the school heads to their personal life satisfaction (F – value = 45.814, Probability = 0.000**) therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance. Moreover, 49.50% of the variation of the life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of professional life satisfaction was accounted by their decision-making confidence. The remaining 50.50% was accounted by some aspects not included in the context of the study. It is established that Academic Leadership, Guidance and Human Resource Management are the best predictor of life satisfaction in terms of personal life satisfaction of the respondents. It implies that school heads with very high confidence in academic leadership, guidance and human resource management have highly satisfactory professional life.

However, there may be other factors that enhance personal life satisfaction apart from Academic Leadership and Guidance and Human Resource Management. According to Bradley and Corwyn, (2004) personal life satisfaction may be enhanced by positive relationships, family environment, peer acceptance and good health. Therefore, Pavot and Diener (1993) suggest that researchers should also assess an individual’s global judgement of his or her life rather than only his or her satisfaction with specific domains. Thus, future research should also examine other variables that have potential in enhancing life satisfaction such as relationship among peers and family, good health, family environment and also personality factors. Diener et al. (2004) concluded that personality factors have more tendencies to be more consistent in relating to life satisfaction than contextual factors.

Table 25 Decision-making confidence and professional life satisfaction

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	1.304	0.211	6.176	0.000
Academic Leadership	0.223	0.077	2.897	0.004**
Governance	0.036	0.085	0.416	0.678
Guidance and HRM	0.311	0.078	3.971	0.000**
Financial and Infra. Mgt.	0.038	0.074	0.520	0.604
External Relations	0.135	0.070	1.912	0.057

R² = 0.495
 Probability = 0.000**

F – Value = 45.814
 ** = Significant at 1% level

Cultural Intelligence and the Life Satisfaction

The influence of cultural intelligence to the life satisfaction of the respondents in terms of personal and professional aspect is presented in the succeeding statements.

Cultural Intelligence and Personal Life Satisfaction

In Table 26, it was revealed that there is a significant influence in the cultural Intelligence of the school heads to their personal life satisfaction (F – value = 2.497, Probability = 0.048*) therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance. Moreover, 28.50% of the variation of the life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of professional life satisfaction was accounted by their cultural intelligence. The remaining 71.50% was accounted by some aspects not included in the context of the study. It is established that Metacognitive and Behavioral Intelligence are the best predictor of life satisfaction in terms of personal life satisfaction of the respondents. It implies that school heads with very high intelligence in terms of metacognitive and behavioral intelligence have highly satisfactory personal life.

Gilman and Huebner (2006) found in their studies that people with high life satisfaction correlates with high academic leadership high interpersonal and intrapersonal functioning than others reporting with low life satisfaction. They also reveal that high levels of life satisfaction and various indices of positive behavioral and psychological adjustment are interrelated.

Table 26 Cultural intelligence and personal life satisfaction

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	3.710	0.729	5.090	0.000
Metacognitive CQ	0.706	0.306	2.302	0.030*
Cognitive CQ	0.325	0.230	1.413	0.170
Motivational CQ	0.020	0.337	0.060	0.952
Behavioural CQ	-0.855	0.407	2.103	0.046*

R² = 0.285
 Probability = 0.048*

F – Value = 2.497
 * = Significant at 5% level

Cultural Intelligent and Professional Life Satisfaction

In Table 26 it was revealed that there is a significant influence in the cultural Intelligence of the school heads to their personal life satisfaction (F – value = 3.041, Probability = 0.036*) therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected since the value of probability is significantly lesser than 0.050 level of significance. The 32.70% of the variation of the life satisfaction of the school heads in terms of professional

life satisfaction was accounted by their cultural intelligence. The remaining 67.30% was accounted by some aspects not included in the context of the study.

It is established that Metacognitive and Behavioral Intelligence are the best predictor of life satisfaction in terms of professional life satisfaction of the respondents. It implies that school heads with very high intelligence in terms of metacognitive and behavioral intelligence have highly satisfactory professional life. The study of Schimmack, (2002) found out that there is a significant positive correlation found between metacognitive intelligence and life satisfaction. Moreover, metacognitive strategies and intelligence regulate cognitive processes and contribute to learning. Understanding the learning processes and information utilization set the stage for the learning to occur; thus, they help the individual hold a positive feeling towards life.

Moreover, Mohri, et al., (2013) believed that people may experience life satisfaction is a stable and general feeling that reflects the attitudes or behavior people hold about the world they live in. Metacognitive strategies help identify the suitable strategy to do a certain task and to assess one's performance so that people may achieve their goals and enjoy life satisfaction.

Table 27 Cultural intelligence and professional life satisfaction

Profiles	Coef. B	Std. Error	t - value	Probability
(Constants)	3.936	0.674	5.837	0.000
Metacognitive CQ	0.671	0.284	2.368	0.026*
Cognitive CQ	0.372	0.213	1.751	0.092
Motivational CQ	-0.017	0.312	-0.055	0.956
Behavioural CQ	-0.867	0.376	2.306	0.030*

R² = 0.327
 Probability = 0.036*

F – Value = 3.041
 * = Significant at 5% level

MODIFIED FRAMEWORK

Figure 3 shows the influence of the socio-demographic profile of the school heads to the decision-making and cultural intelligence of the respondents. It also shows the relationship between decision-making to the cultural intelligence, the influence of the decision-making and cultural intelligence to life satisfaction of the respondents.

SUMMARY

The study was undertaken to look into the socio-demographic profile of the school heads and its influence to the decision-making confidence level and cultural intelligence of the respondents. It also determined the relationship of cultural intelligence to the decision-making confidence; the influence of decision-making confidence and the cultural intelligence (CQ) to the life satisfaction of the school heads.

The study sought to answer the following: the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of; age, gender, ethnicity, years in service, and highest educational attainment; the decision-making confidence of the respondents in terms of Academic Leadership, Governance, Guidance and Human Resource Management, Financial and Infrastructure Management and External Relations; the Cultural Intelligence (CQ) of the respondents in terms of Metacognitive CQ, Cognitive CQ, Motivational CQ and Behavioral CQ; the Life Satisfaction of the respondents in terms of Personal and Professional aspects; the influence of the Socio-Demographic Profile of the respondents to their Decision-making Confidence; the influence of the Socio-demographic Profile of the respondents to their Cultural Intelligence; the significant relationship between the Cultural Intelligence (CQ) and the Decision-making Confidence of the respondents; the influence of the Decision-making Confidence and Cultural Intelligence (CQ) to the Life Satisfaction of the respondents.

The researcher used both the qualitative and quantitative descriptive research. A descriptive-correlational research design was utilized in the study. The respondents of the study were the school heads and teachers of the private schools in Cotabato and Kidapawan city divisions. The study was conducted during the second semester of the school year 2016-2017. Generally, the majority of the respondents were 41 to 50 years old, female, Ilonggo, 14 to 20 years in service and have Master's degree in terms of their age, gender, ethnicity, years in service and highest educational attainment.

The school heads decision-making confidence had a Very High Confidence Level in terms of Academic Leadership, Governance, Guidance and Human Resource Management, Financial and Infrastructure Management and External Relations. The school heads cultural intelligence (CQ) is High Intelligence in terms of Cognitive CQ, Motivational CQ and Behavioral CQ. However, they have a very high Intelligence in terms of Metacognitive CQ.

The school heads life satisfaction level is Highly Satisfactory in terms of personal and professional satisfaction. The Socio-demographic Profile of the respondents significantly influenced their decision-making confidence in terms of academic leadership, guidance and human resource management and external relation. Apparently, it did not significantly influence the decision-making confidence of the respondents in terms of governance, financial and infrastructure management. The Socio-demographic Profile of the respondents significantly influenced their cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive CQ and behavioral CQ. Apparently, it does not significantly influence the cultural intelligence of the respondents in terms of cognitive CQ, and motivational CQ.

There was no significant degree of relationship observed between decision-making confidence in terms of academic leadership, governance, guidance and human resource management, financial and infrastructure management, and cultural intelligence in terms of metacognitive CQ, cognitive CQ, motivational CQ and behavioral CQ of the school heads. Nevertheless, significant degree of relationship is observed between the external relations on decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence in terms of motivational CQ and behavioral CQ of the school heads.

The decision-making confidence of the respondents in terms of academic leadership, guidance and human resource management and external relation significantly influenced their personal and professional life satisfaction. Apparently, no influence was observed on the decision-making confidence of the respondents in terms of governance, financial and infrastructure management to the personal and professional life satisfaction. The cultural intelligence of the respondents in terms of metacognitive and behavioral intelligence significantly influenced their personal and professional life satisfaction. Apparently, no influence was observed on the cognitive and motivational intelligence to the personal and professional life satisfaction of the respondents.

CONCLUSION

This presents the conclusion of the study based on the findings in the previous chapter. The school heads are diverse in their socio-demographic profile. However, they have very high confidence level in all aspects of decision-making and they are culturally competent with highly satisfactory personal and professional life.

The Socio-demographic Profile of the respondents had contributions on the decision-making of the school heads in academic leadership, guidance and human resource management and external relation as well as in their metacognitive and behavioral intelligence.

The academic leadership, guidance and human resource management and external relation as well as the motivational intelligence and behavioral intelligence had contributions to the personal and professional life satisfaction of the school heads. Hence, the school heads with high decision-making confidence and cultural intelligence will have very satisfactory life satisfaction both personal and professional.

RECOMMENDATION

In reference to the aforementioned results and conclusions, the researcher presents the following recommendations.

1. School heads are encouraged enroll in masters, doctoral and post-graduate programs and continue developing their decision-making skills. To further enhance their decision-making confidence the school heads may attend trainings and seminars relative to decision-making.

2. The school heads are encouraged to learn more about cultural intelligence by exposing themselves in a more diverse community. Learn their culture, arts and crafts, marriage systems, legal tradition and beliefs.
3. Develop the school heads external relationships by building more partnerships with businesses, industries and cultural communities. Through this, the school heads will be able to enhance their cultural intelligence.
4. Continue improving their decision-making confidence and continue finding life satisfaction by fulfilling their personal and professional dreams and aspirations.
5. Enhance the school heads cultural intelligence by exposing them to people with different culture which are not familiar to them. Interact with people from other cultural groups and become culturally competent individuals.
6. Conduct the study to the public-school heads.

REFERENCES

- ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics). (1998). *Education and training in Australia* (Cat. No. 4224.0). Australian Bureau of Statistics. <http://www.abs.gov.au>
- Ang, S., & Van Dyne, L. (2008). *Handbook on cultural intelligence: Theory, measurement and applications*. M.E. Sharpe.
- Ang, S., Van Dyne, L., Koh, C. K. S., Ng, K. Y., Templer, K. J., Tay, C., & Chandrasekar, N. A. (2007). Cultural intelligence: Its measurement and effects on cultural judgment and decision making, cultural adaptation, and task performance. *Management and Organization Review*, 3(3), 335–371.
- Archaya, D. R., Bell, J. S., Simkhada, P., Van Teijlingen, E. R., & Regmi, P. R. (2010). Women’s autonomy in decision-making: A demographic study in Nepal. *Reproductive Health*, 7(15). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-7-15>
- Bengtsson, M., et al. (2005). The reversal of gender inequalities in higher education. <http://monitor.icef.com/2014/10/women-increasingly-outpacing-mens-higher-education-participation-many-world-markets/>
- Boundless. (2016, September 20). *Theories of multiple intelligence*. Boundless Psychology. <https://www.boundless.com/psychology/textbooks/boundless-psychology-textbook/intelligence-11/introduction-to-intelligence-61/theories-of-multiple-intelligence-240-12775/>
- Bradley, R. H., & Corwyn, R. F. (2004). Life satisfaction among European American, African American, Chinese American, Mexican American, and Dominican American adolescents. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 28(5), 385–400.
- Brislin, R., Worthley, R., & Macnab, B. (2006). *Cultural intelligence: Understanding behaviors that serve people’s goals*. Stanford University Press.
- Catalyst. (2004). *Women and men in U.S. corporate leadership: Same workplace, different realities?* <http://www.catalyst.org>
- Catalyst. (2007). *The bottom line: Corporate performance and women’s representation on boards*.
- Chemaly, S. (2016). At work as at home, men reap the benefits of women’s “invisible labor.” *Quartz*. <https://qz.com/599999/>
- Cheung, F., & Lucas, R. E. (2014). Assessing the validity of single-item life satisfaction measures. *International Journal of Educational Studies*, 5(6), 1–10.
- Croson, R., & Gneezy, U. (2009). Gender differences in preferences. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 47(2), 448–474.

- Diener, E., & Diener, C. (1996). Most people are happy. *Psychological Science*, 7(3), 181–185.
- Earley, P. C., & Ang, S. (2003). *Cultural intelligence: Individual interactions across cultures*. Stanford University Press.
- Earley, P. C., Ang, S., & Tan, J. S. (2006). *Developing cultural intelligence at work*. Stanford University Press.
- Earley, P. C., & Mosakowski, E. (2005). Cultural intelligence. *Harvard Business Review*, 82(10), 139–146.
- European Commission. (2012). *Women in economic decision-making in the EU: Progress report*. Publications Office of the European Union. <http://ec.europa.eu>
- Gilman, R., & Huebner, E. S. (2006). Characteristics of adolescents who report very high life satisfaction. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 35, 311–319.
- Groysberg, B. (2013). *Gender differences in leadership styles and the impact within corporate boards*. Harvard Business School.
- Harvard Family Research Project. (2010). *Partnerships for learning: Promising practices in integrating school and out-of-school time program supports*. <http://www.hfrp.org>
- Janssens, M., & Brett, J. M. (2006). Cultural intelligence in global teams: A fusion model of collaboration. *Group & Organization Management*, 31, 124–153.
- Kong, F., Zhao, J., & You, X. (2012). Emotional intelligence and life satisfaction in Chinese university students. *Chinese University Journal*.
- Ladd, H. F. (2008). *Value-added modeling of teacher credentials: Policy implications*. CALDER Center.
- Law, K. S., Wong, C. S., & Huang, G. H. (2008). The effects of emotional intelligence on job performance and life satisfaction. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 25, 51–69.
- Little, P. (2011a). School-community learning partnerships: Essential to expanded learning success. <http://expandinglearning.org>
- Little, P. (2011b). Expanded learning opportunities in Washington state: Pathways to student success. <http://www.schoolsoutwashington.org>
- Livermore, D. (2010). *Leading with cultural intelligence: The new secret to success*. AMACOM.
- Livermore, D. (2011). *The cultural intelligence difference*. AMACOM.
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370–396.

- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. Harper & Row.
- Maslow, A. H. (1962). *Toward a psychology of being*. D. Van Nostrand.
- Maslow, A. H. (1970). *Religions, values, and peak experiences*. Penguin. (Original work published 1964)
- Ng, K. Y., Van Dyne, L., & Ang, S. (2009). Beyond international experience. *Human Resource Management, 48*(4), 511–529.
- Ng, K. Y., Van Dyne, L., & Ang, S. (2009). From experience to experiential learning. *Academy of Management Learning & Education, 8*, 511–526.
- Office of the Public Advocate. (2012). *Educational attainment of people with impaired decision-making capacity*. <http://www.justice.qld.gov.au>
- Pavot, W., & Diener, E. (1993). Review of the satisfaction with life scale. *Psychological Assessment, 5*, 164–172.
- Scutti, S. (2013). Decision-making ability may decline with age. *Medical Daily*. <http://www.medicaldaily.com>
- Sternberg, R. J., & Grigorenko, E. L. (2006). Cultural intelligence and successful intelligence. *Group & Organization Management, 31*, 27–39.
- Thomas, D. C., & Inkson, K. (2009). *Cultural intelligence: Living and working globally*. Berrett-Koehler.
- Van Dyne, L., Ang, S., & Koh, C. (2008). Development and validation of the CQS. In S. Ang & L. Van Dyne (Eds.), *Handbook on cultural intelligence* (pp. 217–227). M.E. Sharpe.
- Worthy, D. A. (2011). Decision-making changes with age—and age helps! *Psychological Science*.
- Yap, R. (2011). Working women still do housework. *Daily Mail*. <http://www.dailymail.co.uk>